

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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PILOT IMPLEMENTATION OF A LOW-LITERACY ZONE TOOL
FOR HEART FAILURE SELF-MANAGEMENT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the Degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Background: Heart failure (HF) affects 6.5 million Americans, with one million hospitalizations, a 21.9% readmission rate, and \$30 billion in healthcare costs. Self-care support tools with color-coded zones (green = stable; yellow = caution; red = take action) can help patients recognize and respond to HF symptoms and reduce readmissions and costs. Studies are lacking on zone tools' impact on HF self-care and quality of life (QoL).

Purpose: The purpose of this evidence-based practice project was to test the effect of a low-literacy zone tool for HF self-management on self-care and quality of life.

Methods: The author led an inter-disciplinary palliative care (PC) team in adapting an existing green-yellow-red zone tool for HF self-management. Participants were randomly assigned to a control group receiving usual care or an intervention group receiving the zone tool plus usual care. HF self-care and HF-related quality of life were measured respectively with the Self-Care of Heart Failure Index (SCHFI) and the Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire (KCCQ-12), at baseline and at 30 and 60 days.

Results: Due to the limited sample size, the findings of this pilot project were inconclusive regarding the effect of the HF zone tool on the outcomes of interest.

Implications for Practice: This EBP pilot project demonstrated the feasibility of developing and implementing a zone tool for HF self-management for patients with advanced HF in a home-based palliative care (PC) program. Further research is needed with larger samples to assess zone tools' effect on self-care and quality of life.

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BACKGROUND

As our nation's elderly population continues to grow, many Americans are living with one or more chronic illnesses. According to the most recent National Vital Statistics Report, diseases of the heart remained first among the leading causes of death for all Americans in 2014, although the death rate from heart disease has decreased fairly steadily since 1980 (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2016). In 2012, heart disease accounted for 25.7% of deaths for persons age 65 and over and 29.6% of deaths for persons age 85 and over (CDC, 2015). One of the most prevalent cardiovascular diseases is heart failure, a progressive, chronic illness in which the heart muscle is unable to pump enough blood to meet the body's needs for blood and oxygen (National Heart, Lung & Blood Institute, 2015). Signs and symptoms of heart failure include: weight gain, shortness of breath (particularly with exertion or lying supine), leg edema, and fatigue (American Heart Association, 2016).

Heart failure (HF) affects an estimated 6.5 million people age 20+, with nearly one million new cases diagnosed annually. The number of Americans with HF is projected to increase to more than 8 million people by the year 2030. HF is the primary cause of nearly 69,000 deaths per year in our country (Benjamin et al, 2017). Each year in the U.S., HF results in over one million hospitalizations, with more than \$30 billion in annual costs (Mozaffarian et al., 2015). HF is one of the most common reasons those aged 65 and over are hospitalized (Hall, DeFrances, & Williams, 2010). The current national 30-day readmission rate for HF is 21.9% (U.S. Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services, 2017). Patients with advanced HF have increased symptom burden and decreased quality of life (Blinderman, Homel, Billings, Portenoy, & Tennstedt,

2008). Palliative care can help decrease symptom burden and depression and enhance quality of life in HF patients (Brannstrom & Borman, 2014; Evangelista, et al., 2012).

A key component of most palliative care programs for HF patients is education in self-care (which some authors call self-management). Self-care programs and home-visiting programs for HF patients decrease all-cause hospital readmissions and HF readmissions, resulting in significant cost savings (Cassel et al., 2016; Feltner et al., 2014; Jovicic, Holroyd-Leduc, & Straus, 2006). In order to manage advanced HF effectively at home and avoid decompensation that could lead to hospitalization, patients need to be engaged in self-care. HF self-care behavior includes medication and dietary adherence, recognition of HF symptoms, and contacting or visiting a healthcare provider in order to appropriately adjust treatment (Bui & Forarow, 2012).

Problem Statement

Most elderly HF patients do not contact their healthcare providers in a timely manner due to lack of knowledge and/or failure to recognize early warning signs of HF exacerbation (Jurgens, Lee, Reitano, & Riegel, 2013). Older patients have particular difficulty recognizing and responding appropriately to symptoms leading to decompensation (Falk, Ekman, Anderson, Fu, & Granger, 2013; Riegel et al., 2010). When patients recognize and report signs and symptoms of early HF exacerbation to their healthcare providers in order to adjust their treatment plan appropriately, they can avoid hospitalization, decrease symptom burden and maintain or improve their quality of life (Wakefield, Groves, Drwal, Scherubel, & Kaboli, 2016). Therefore, patients with advanced heart failure need appropriate education and useful decision-support tools to enhance their symptom recognition and thereby improve their self-care.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this evidence-based practice project was to test the effect of a low-literacy zone tool for heart failure self-management on HF self-care and quality of life.

Goals/Objectives of Project

1. Implement a low-literacy HF Zones for Self-management decision-support tool that instructs patients/caregivers regarding HF self-care, signs and symptoms of HF exacerbation, and when to contact their nurse.
2. Evaluate impact of the HF zone tool on patients' self-care and quality of life (QoL).
 - a. Measure outcomes of interest (HF self-care and HF-related QoL) before implementing the HF zone tool.
 - b. Measure these outcomes approximately 30 and 60 days' post-implementation.
 - c. Compare outcomes of interest between intervention and control groups.
3. Identify correlations between demographic factors and outcomes of interest.
4. Evaluate the ease of reading and helpfulness (feasibility) for participants and nurses of the HF zone tool and the usual care decision-support handout.
5. Evaluate the ease of understanding and completion (feasibility) for participants and nurses of the measurement tools used in this pilot project.

Local Context and Significance of Project

Sharp Healthcare is a non-profit integrated health system and the largest healthcare provider in San Diego County, California. Since 1991, Sharp HospiceCare has been providing end-of-life care and support to Sharp's patients and their loved ones.

Sharp HospiceCare's Transitions program (where the author serves as a Clinical Nurse), was developed in 2005 and first implemented in 2007. Transitions is an innovative model of care that addresses the needs of patients with advanced chronic illness. The four pillars of the Transitions program are: (1) in-home consultation, (2) evidence-based medical prognostication, (3) caregiver support, and (4) advance care planning (Hoefler, Johnson, & Bender, 2013).

Two recent studies found significant decreases in hospitalization and costs of care among Sharp Transitions patients. A preliminary evaluation of the Transitions program from January, 2008 through December, 2010 found that this model of home-based palliative care significantly decreased hospitalization rates from 32% to 17% and ED visit rates from 57% to 31%. Total costs of care per patient were significantly reduced from \$73,025 before Transitions enrollment to \$46,588 after enrollment (Hoefler et al., 2013).

Cassel et al. (2016) conducted a retrospective, observational study of the Transitions program from 2007 through 2014 using healthcare claims data for Medicare Advantage patients whose date of death was known, who had one of four target chronic diseases: Cancer, COPD, HF, or Dementia, and had two years of claims data available prior to death. This study found that Transitions patients' hospital costs per month, rates of hospitalization, and percentages of patients dying in the hospital were all significantly less than those for matched comparison patients for all four diagnosis categories. The Transitions program costs (\$642 per member per month) were far less than the healthcare costs avoided (>\$3,000 per member per month) with “return on investment” of 4.2 - 6.6.

The Sharp Transitions team consists of nurses, social workers, physicians, and spiritual care counselors. Transitions' primary goals are: (1) educate patients and

caregivers on disease process, symptom recognition, diet and medication management, (2) enhance care coordination with patients' primary care and specialty providers, (3) help patients and caregivers develop long-term plans of care aligned with their values and preferences, and (4) facilitate a smooth transfer to hospice care when appropriate (Hoefler et al., 2013). Another key goal of Transitions is to improve self-care and quality of life for patients with advanced illness. This pilot project sought to determine if a zone tool for HF self-management could help patients to achieve this goal.

Conceptual Framework

The primary theoretical framework for this doctoral project was the Situation-Specific Theory of Heart Failure Self-Care. This theory was originally published by Riegel and Dickson in 2008 and then revised and updated by Riegel, Dickson and Faulkner in 2016. Their theory applied the concept of Naturalistic Decision Making (NDM), described by Lipshitz, Klein, Orasanu, and Salas (2001), that helped explain how individuals make meaningful decisions in real-world settings.

Original Situation-Specific Theory of Heart Failure Self-Care

As Riegel and Dickson (2008) applied NDM to their original theory, they explained that the situational elements of person, problem and environment influence the HF self-care decision-making process. This process involves experience, knowledge, skills, and values, which impact decisions about self-care. In their original Situation-Specific Theory of Heart Failure Self-Care, Riegel and Dickson (2008) defined self-care as "a naturalistic decision-making process involving the choice of behaviors that maintain physiologic stability (maintenance) and the response to symptoms when they occur (management)" (p. 190).

The self-care maintenance process involves symptom monitoring and treatment adherence. Self-care management begins with symptom recognition, which leads to use of self-care treatments and treatment evaluation. In the original theory, self-care confidence moderates and/or mediates the relationship between self-care maintenance and self-care management (Riegel & Dickson, 2008).

Revised Situation-Specific Theory of Heart Failure Self-Care

Riegel, Dickson, and Faulkner (2016) revised and updated their original theory based on their further research. They reported that they made three revisions to the original theory: (1) adding a new concept reflecting the process of self-perception; (2) including both autonomous and consultative aspects to each self-care process; and (3) describing a closer link between self-care processes and naturalistic decision-making.

In the revised theory, the first essential self-care process is *maintenance*, which includes treatment adherence and healthy behaviors, such as taking medications, exercising, and following a low-sodium diet. The second self-care process is *symptom perception*, which includes detection and interpretation of physical sensations. This involves body listening, monitoring signs, recognizing, interpreting and labeling symptoms of heart failure (HF). The third process is *management*, the person's response to their symptoms. All three of these self-care processes involve autonomous and consultative self-care behaviors. Autonomous behaviors are based on independent decisions, while consultative behaviors involve seeking the advice of a health professional before acting (Riegel et al., 2016).

Support for Theory of HF Self-Care

In their article which presented and explained their revised and updated theory, Riegel et al. (2016) performed a literature search using several databases as well as Google Scholar to identify articles that cited their original Situation-Specific Theory of Heart Failure Self-Care. They ultimately analyzed a total of 85 studies that cited their original theory. They noted that most of these studies applied or tested a portion of their overall theory, rather than their entire theory.

In one of these studies, Seto et al. (2011) examined the relationship between self-care and health-related quality of life (HRQoL) among HF outpatients. They applied the original Situation-specific Theory of Heart Failure Self-care by utilizing the Self-Care of Heart Failure Index (SCHFI). Determinants of HRQoL were older age, greater self-care confidence, better functional capacity, and fewer comorbidities. In the qualitative portion of their study, the authors also found that HRQoL was also associated with higher self-care confidence. Barriers to self-care included lack of self-care education, financial constraints, lack of perceived benefit and lower self-efficacy.

A secondary analysis of four mixed-methods studies applied the theory of HF self-care to test the moderating effect of comorbidity on the relationship between self-efficacy and self-care in HF patients. Comorbidity influenced the relationship between self-efficacy and self-care maintenance, only when levels of comorbidity were moderately high. The authors concluded that methods of improving self-efficacy may improve self-care in patients with multiple comorbidities (Dickson, Buck, & Riegel, 2013). These studies both applied the Situation-Specific Theory of HF Self-Care to understand which factors impact HF self-care and HRQoL.

Applying Conceptual Framework to Project

Since one of the major outcomes that this doctoral project examined was HF self-care, the Situation-Specific Theory of Heart Failure Self-Care served as the central theoretical framework for the project. This theory is the foundation for the Self-Care of Heart Failure Index (SCHFI), a tool originally presented thirteen years ago (Riegel et al., 2004) and then updated five years later (Riegel, Lee, Dickson, & Carlson, 2009a). The tool's most recent version (SCHFI v.6.2, published in 2009) includes three subscales corresponding to the three domains of HF self-care (maintenance, management, and confidence) that are included in the original Situation-Specific Theory of Heart Failure Self-Care. On her website, Riegel (2015) indicates that this tool is currently being revised and updated to include the newest HF self-care domain of symptom perception, but this updated tool is not yet published or available in the public domain.

By using SCHFI v.6.2 to measure HF self-care, this doctoral project applied the original Situation-Specific Theory of Heart Failure Self-Care. From the perspective of the revised and updated version of this theory, the adapted HF zone tool is intended to help Transitions patients improve their self-care maintenance, symptom perception, and self-care management behaviors in response to their perception. The zone tool was also designed to help patients and/or caregivers understand when they need to contact their Transitions nurse for advice on how to modify their self-care, which involves the consultative aspect of self-care management. This doctoral project thus applied both the original and revised versions of the Situation-Specific Theory of Heart Failure Self-Care. According to the revised theory (Riegel, Dickson, and Faulkner, 2016), symptom perception mediates the relationship between self-care maintenance and self-care

management. The Modified Self-Care of HF Model shown in Figure 1 depicts this mediated relationship and shows how the zone tool is designed to facilitate self-care maintenance, symptom perception, and self-care management.

Modified Self-Care of HF Model

(Adapted from Riegel, Dickson, & Faulkner, 2016)

Figure 1. Modified self-care of HF model.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to examine and synthesize recent evidence pertaining to the key elements of this doctoral project, utilizing the following databases: CINAHL Plus with Full Text, PubMed, Academic Search Premier, PsycINFO, Social Sciences with Full Text, and Google Scholar. Key MeSH search terms were: heart failure, congestive heart failure, self-care, self-management, quality of life, health-related quality of life, health literacy, readmissions, palliative care, chronic disease, health outcomes, determinants, measurement tools, Self-Care of Heart Failure Index, Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire, Newest Vital Sign, psychometric testing, red yellow green, symptom monitoring, zone tool, randomized control trial, systematic review, integrative review. This literature review focused on recent studies presenting evidence in each of these key topic areas:

1. Significance of HF self-care and impact on health outcomes
2. Barriers and facilitators of HF self-care
3. Interventions to promote HF self-care
4. Interventions using green-yellow-red zone tools for HF self-care

Significance of Heart Failure Self-Care and Impact on Health Outcomes

As previously mentioned, Riegel and Dickson (2008) explained that self-care is a naturalistic decision-making process of choosing behaviors to maintain health-related stability (maintenance) and responding to symptoms as they occur (management). Schulman-Green et al. (2012) performed a qualitative meta-synthesis of 101 studies examining processes of self-management (also known as self-care) in chronic illness.

They identified three main categories of self-management processes: (1) focusing on illness needs; (2) activating resources; (3) living with chronic illness. They recommended that healthcare providers can better facilitate patients' self-management by helping them coordinate their self-care activities, recognizing how different self-care activities vary over time in importance to patients, and communicating with patients and providers to help create appropriate self-management plans.

Buck et al. (2012) examined the relationship between HF self-care (as measured with the SCHFI) and HRQoL (as measured with the Minnesota Living with Heart Failure Questionnaire). They found a significant positive correlation between higher self-care confidence and greater total, physical, and emotional HRQoL. They found no significant correlation between self-care maintenance and self-care management and HRQoL.

In their scientific statement on promoting self-care among HF patients, Riegel et al. (2009b) summarized clinical evidence on: (1) self-care behaviors that HF patients need to perform; (2) potential barriers to HF self-care; (3) interventions designed to improve HF self-care; (4) the effect of HF self-care on outcomes. HF patients need to follow providers' advice on medications, diet, and exercise, perform preventive behaviors, and self-monitor for HF signs and symptoms. Many HF patients delay for days before calling their nurse or provider, which may be due to failure to self-monitor for early HF symptoms or inability to recognize and interpret those symptoms.

Barriers and Facilitators of Heart Failure Self-Care

In the above-noted scientific statement, Riegel et al. (2009b) identified several potential barriers to HF self-care: comorbidities, depression, anxiety, cognitive impairment, sleep disturbances, older age, poor health literacy, and problems with the

healthcare system. They also listed interventions that promote HF self-care: skill development (particularly the ability to recognize and respond appropriately to early HF symptoms), deliberate behavior change, family support, and improved systems of care (disease management and care coordination in transitions across settings). This summary found that improved HF self-care reduced HF-related hospitalizations and all-cause hospitalizations, lowered HF inpatient costs, and improved HRQoL.

As noted above, low health literacy is a key barrier to effective HF self-care. Health literacy is defined as “the degree to which individuals have the capacity to obtain, process, and understand basic health information and services needed to make appropriate health decisions” (U.S. Dept. of Health & Human Services, 2000). In a consensus statement of the Heart Failure Society of America, Evangelista et al. (2010) reported that low health literacy was associated with decreased knowledge of one's health condition, poor medication recall and adherence to treatment plans, poor self-care behaviors, decreased physical and mental health, and increased rates of hospitalization and mortality. Low health literacy has been associated with lower HF knowledge, self-efficacy and self-care behaviors, as well as poor HF-related quality of life (Macabasco-O'Connell et al., 2011). Wu et al. (2013) also found that low literacy increased HF patients' risks for HF-related hospitalization and all-cause hospitalization or death. Evangelista et al. (2010) recommended timely recognition of low health literacy plus tailored interventions to help HF patients with low literacy achieve better self-care and improved outcomes.

Several studies examined other factors that adversely impact HF self-care. In a qualitative meta-analysis of three of their mixed-methods studies, Dickson, Buck, and

Riegel (2011) found that HF patients with multiple comorbidities were more vulnerable to poor self-care, due to fragmented self-care instructions for their multiple conditions and attitudes regarding the need to prioritize self-care for one condition vs. another. In a secondary analysis of four mixed-methods studies, Dickson, Buck, and Riegel (2013) found that comorbidity adversely impacted the relationship between self-efficacy and self-care maintenance, and they recommended working to enhance self-efficacy to improve self-care in HF patients with multiple comorbidities.

A mixed methods study of 30 African-American HF patients found that subjects' self-care (as measured by the Self-Care of Heart Failure Index) was influenced by cultural beliefs about HF and by social norms. Cultural beliefs supported some self-care behaviors, such as medication adherence. Social norms made it difficult for subjects to reconcile adherence to a low-salt diet with their culture-based food preferences (Dickson, McCarthy, Howe, Schipper, & Katz, 2013).

In another mixed-methods study of 41 adults, Dickson, Lee and Riegel (2011) found that lack of understanding, not lack of knowledge, contributed to poor self-care. Interestingly, they also noted that patients with poorer cognitive function showed better self-care, which they attributed to these patients relying more on supportive spouses or other caregivers to help them manage their HF. A systematic review by Buck et al. (2015) found that caregivers contributed substantively to HF patients' self-care, through concrete activities such as weighing patients to interpersonal activities such as facilitating understanding of self-care needs.

Zavertnik's (2014) systematic review determined that age-related symptoms, social issues, and cognitive factors were barriers to self-care, and education on self-care

knowledge and telemonitoring to augment symptom recognition were facilitators of self-care. Currie et al. (2012) conducted a systematic review of 24 qualitative studies, which found that poor patient-provider communication and lack of provider continuity were barriers to HF self-care. They also noted that patients' HF self-care was better when they perceived that their providers were responsive, interested in their needs, and shared information well with them. Based on these studies, Transitions nurses need to engage in active listening and supportive communication with HF patients and their caregivers to help facilitate their HF self-care.

Interventions to Promote Heart Failure Self-Care

Several recent systematic and integrative reviews examined the impact of various types of interventions on HF self-care, HRQoL, and the impact of self-care on health outcomes. Jonkman et al. (2016) found that HF self-management interventions reduced HF-related hospitalization, HF hospitalization or all-cause death, and these interventions produced small but significant improvement in HF-related quality of life. A Cochrane Review of 41 randomized-control trials (RCT's) found moderate-quality evidence that non-invasive home telemonitoring (NIHT) and structured telephone support (STS) reduced all-cause mortality and HF-related hospitalizations, and improved HF knowledge and HF self-care (Inglis et al, 2015).

In their systematic review and meta-analysis, Feltner et al. (2014) found that home visiting programs and multi-disciplinary (MDS) HF clinics reduced all-cause mortality, and home-visiting programs reduced HF-specific readmission. STS reduced HF-specific readmission but not all-cause readmission. Home-visiting programs, MDS-HF clinics, and STS all reduced mortality, while neither NIHT nor primary education

interventions reduced mortality or readmissions. These findings help explain the efficacy of the Sharp Transitions program in reducing readmission, as Transitions provides multi-disciplinary home visits and STS to promote HF self-care.

Another integrative review determined that HF self-care interventions resulted in improved self-care behaviors, as well as higher HF knowledge, self-care knowledge, increased self-efficacy, and improved QoL. HF self-care interventions also decreased readmissions, lowered inpatient costs, and increased median time to clinical event (death or hospitalization) (Barnason, Zimmerman, & Young, 2012). All of these systematic and integrative reviews and meta-analyses focused on interventions designed to improve HF self-care and QoL, which were the primary outcomes of interest for this pilot project.

Two RCT's examined interventions to improve HF self-care and QoL. Clark et al. (2015) found that a home-based education support intervention (with built-in memory enhancement methods) by APRN's improved HF self-care, along with QoL, emotional state and metamemory. This study utilized the SCHFI to measure HF self-care, as well as the KCCQ to measure QoL, which were both used in this doctoral project. Another pilot study which utilized SCHFI and KCCQ found that a community-based skill building intervention delivered by lay health educators in three community senior centers resulted in significant improvements over time in HF self-care, HF knowledge, and QoL with moderate to large effect sizes (Dickson et al., 2014).

Jurgens, Lee, Reitano, and Riegel (2013) conducted an RCT examining the effect of a HF symptom monitoring and response training on HF self-care (as measured by the SCHFI). At 90 days, they found that intervention on the symptom training significantly

improved self-care maintenance and response compared to usual care. They recommended further investigation of symptom monitoring strategies on self-care.

Interventions Using Green-Yellow-Red Zone Tools for Heart Failure Self-Care

A zone tool may be used for self-care education and decision-support to help patients with a variety of chronic conditions (asthma, diabetes, COPD, HF, etc.) better recognize signs and symptoms of an exacerbation and take appropriate action. These tools use three color-coded zones to rank symptoms in degree of severity: green=symptoms mild (condition stable); yellow=symptoms moderate (early exacerbation); red=symptoms severe (advanced exacerbation). Several online examples of HF self-management zone tools guide patients and caregivers in self-monitoring and recognizing signs and symptoms of HF exacerbations (AHA, 2015; MacColl Center for Healthcare Innovation, 1996-2017; Sutter Center for Integrated Care, 2013; Visiting Nurses Association of America, 2016).

Few published studies examine the effects of zone tools on HF outcomes. DeWalt et al. (2006) tested a low-literacy intervention, which included a one-hour education session and provided patients a digital scale and picture-based HF education booklet. This booklet featured a green-yellow-red zone tool that instructed patients to adjust their diuretic dose daily, based on their weight that day. The intervention also included scheduled follow up phone calls by the program coordinator for up to six months. At 12 months, the intervention group had lower rates of hospitalization or death and higher rates of daily weight monitoring than the controls.

A one-year multisite RCT of a single session versus a multisession HF self-care intervention featuring a similar green-yellow-red HF zone tool found no difference

overall between the single-session and multisession groups in all-cause hospitalization and death (DeWalt et al., 2012). Among those with low literacy, the multisession intervention group had lower incidence than the single-session group of all-cause hospitalization and death, while higher-literacy subjects had a higher incidence in the multisession group than the single-session group of all-cause hospitalization and death. HF-related quality of life (HFQoL) showed greater improvement at one and six months in the multisession group than in the single session group, but the difference was smaller at 12 months.

Beside these two studies by DeWalt & colleagues, this writer found one other recent clinical study, one feasibility study, and two pilot studies of self-care interventions using zone tools with HF patients. An evidence-based HF education intervention using a green-yellow-red zone tool significantly reduced HF readmissions at one Florida hospital (Simpson, 2014). A feasibility study used a weight monitoring tool with green, yellow, and red zones, plus a Borg scale to self-monitor shortness of breath. While the participants did use these two tools to self-monitor weight and shortness of breath, they did not increase their reporting of their increased weight and shortness of breath to their providers. (Wakefield, Groves, Drwal, Scherubel, & Kaboli, 2016). One pilot program provided inpatient and outpatient care coordination, a HF education booklet, and a green-yellow-red zone tool on a refrigerator magnet to increase recognition of HF symptoms vs. usual care. This intervention increased use of a home scale, daily weight recording, and practice of new or different health behaviors (Shaw, O'Neal, Siddharthan, & Neugaard, 2014). A pilot study of home automated telemanagement (HAT) featuring a green-

yellow-red zone tool found that the HAT system made it easy and convenient to perform daily self-monitoring and receive daily HF education (Finkelstein & Wood, 2013).

While several zone tools for HF self-management are available online, there is no research regarding the impact of these tools on HF self-care or quality of life. The few published studies on zone tool interventions in this literature review primarily focused on the outcomes of HF readmissions, all-cause hospitalizations or death. This pilot EBP project began to fill the knowledge gap on the effect of a zone tool for HF self-management on HF self-care and quality of life.

METHODS

Project Development

The purpose of this doctoral project was to examine the effect of a zone tool for HF self-management on self-care and quality of life for palliative care patients with advanced HF. This section describes the methods used in this doctoral project. It presents details of each of these project components: design, setting, review and approval, participants and recruitment, protection of participants, design of the HF zone tool, randomization of participants, usual care, intervention, measurement instruments, project implementation, data collection, and data analysis.

Design

This project was designed as an evidence-based practice (EBP) pilot to implement and evaluate a Heart Failure (HF) Zones for Self-management tool adapted for home-based palliative care patients in the Sharp Transitions program (Project Goal 1). The primary outcomes of interest were HF self-care, as measured by SCHFI v.6.2 or CC-SCHFI, and HF-specific quality of life (QoL) as measured by KCCQ-12. This project utilized a randomized control design to compare the zone tool's effect with the effect of usual care on these outcomes (Project Goal 2) at 30 and 60 days' post-implementation.

It examined the effects of demographic and person factors on HF self-care and QoL (Project Goal 3). The pilot EBP project evaluated the readability and helpfulness for HF patients/caregivers and nurses of the new zone tool and the usual care decision-support tool and for Transitions nurses (Project Goal 4). It also evaluated the ease of understanding and completion of the three measurement tools for patients/caregivers and nurses (Project Goal 5).

Setting

Sharp Transitions program is a service of Sharp HospiceCare, which is a department of Sharp Grossmont Hospital in La Mesa, CA. Transitions provides home-based palliative care in mainly urban and suburban areas of San Diego County, primarily to elderly (age 65+) Medicare Advantage patients. Transitions team members visit patients in their residence, which may be a private home or a residential care facility for the elderly (RCFE), such as a board and care or assisted living setting.

Review and Approval

Prior to implementation, the author and project lead (PL) submitted and presented the project proposal to three separate institutional committees for review, revision, and approval. Since the project was designed to be implemented with patients of the Sharp Transitions program, the project proposal was first reviewed and approved by the Sharp Grossmont Hospital Interdisciplinary Research and EBP Council (Appendix A-1). Next the project received approval from the Sharp System Nursing Research and EBP Committee (Appendix A-2). This committee later confirmed the need to obtain informed consent from participants (Appendix A-3). Then the PL submitted the project to the California State University (CSU) Fullerton Institutional Review Board (IRB) for review, further revisions, and final approval (Appendix A-4).

Project Participants**Recruitment**

Participants for this project were recruited from the population of newly and currently enrolled Transitions HF patients. The Transitions nurses described and explained the project, answered patients' and caregivers' questions, and asked if they

wished to participate. Interested patients and relatives/caregivers then received a printed informed consent letter (Appendix B) from the Transitions nurse.

The informed consent letter described the project and informed patients and relatives/caregivers that participation in this project was voluntary and they could withdraw from the project at any time without impacting their care. This letter identified the project lead (PL) and faculty chair with their respective contact information, and it was worded to minimize any potential appearance of coercion of patients to participate. Those who chose to participate provided their written informed consent to the nurse.

Protection of Participants

For this pilot project, the author took precautions to maintain participants' privacy and confidentiality. Each project participant received a unique identification (ID) number that was different from their Transitions or Sharp medical record numbers. Demographic data for the sample were aggregated to avoid identifying individual subjects. Hand-written records were stored in a locked cabinet in the Transitions office and destroyed after completion of the project. Further protection of human subjects was achieved through current, commonly accepted research ethics and the Sharp Nursing Research and EBP Committee and CSU Fullerton IRB review and approval processes.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria for this project were: English-speaking, elderly adult patients (age 65+), newly or currently enrolled in Sharp Transitions program, with a primary Transitions diagnosis of advanced HF, i.e., New York Heart Association (NYHA) Stage 3, as determined by their primary doctor or cardiologist. Exclusion criteria were: comorbidity of moderate to severe dementia (as diagnosed by PCP or neurologist,

admission to Hospice within 60 days of enrollment in this project, and minimal health literacy (score of 0-1 on Newest Vital Sign screening test). Also excluded were patients admitted to Sharp Grossmont Hospital after September 1, 2016 with HF as their primary or secondary admitting diagnosis, since these hospitalized patients were being recruited for a similar concurrent HF study at this hospital.

Randomization

Using a computer-generated program for random number selection (Random.org, 2017), the Transitions patients who agreed to participate in this pilot project were randomly assigned to either the control group or intervention group. Both groups received the usual care that Transitions nurses were currently providing to HF patients, as described in the Usual Care section below. The intervention group received usual care plus the new zone tool for HF self-management, the primary intervention evaluated for this project.

Zone Tool Development and Implementation

Development of HF Zone Tool

This new zone tool was adapted by the PL and Transitions team from the "Congestive Heart Failure Zones for Management" tool (Appendix C-1) posted on the Visiting Nurses Association of America (VNAA) Blueprint for Excellence website (VNAA, 2016). The Blueprint for Excellence is a quality improvement and best practices resource for home health, hospice and palliative care providers. Written permission to use and adapt their HF zone tool (Appendix C-2) was obtained from Liza Greenberg, Interim Vice President, Quality and Performance Improvement at VNAA.

In the new adapted zone tool (Appendix D-1), when patients' symptoms are stable (absent or mild), they are said to be in the "Green Zone: All Clear" and instructed to continue to monitor their weight and symptoms daily, maintain a low-sodium diet, take their HF medications as ordered, and perform physical activity as tolerated. When these symptoms are moderately increased, patients are said to be in the "Yellow Zone: Caution" and instructed to contact their Transitions nurse. This results in the nurse instructing the patient/caregiver by phone on how to relieve their increased symptoms, usually by temporarily increasing their diuretic dose on an as-needed (PRN) basis, as ordered by their provider, and then following up with a home visit within one or two working days to reassess the patient's condition and re-instruct them in HF self-care.

When the patients' symptoms are even more severe, they are said to be in the "Red Zone: Medical Alert" and are instructed to call their Transitions nurse immediately. The nurse would make a home visit the same day or within 24 hours to help the patients treat their severe symptoms at home and avoid an emergency room (ER) visit or hospitalization. The Transitions nurse works to help patients relieve their HF symptoms and if possible, avoid using the ER or hospital to manage their HF exacerbation.

In the process of developing the HF Zones for Self-management tool, the Transitions team deliberately chose very simple language to meet the needs of a low-literacy population. Consequently, the "Show readability statistics" function in the Spelling and Grammar section of Microsoft Word 2016 shows that the main body of the Transitions adapted zone tool (interior section of the zone tool pamphlet) has a Flesch Reading Ease score of 88.6 out of a possible 100. Higher scores on this scale indicate that a text is easier to read. The readability statistics feature in Word also shows that the

main body of the adapted HF zone tool has a Flesch-Kincaid grade level of 1.5. This measure rates text on a U.S. school grade reading level. For example, a Flesch-Kincaid score of 2.0 means that a second grader can understand the document (Microsoft, 2016).

Usual Care

All patients received weekly or biweekly home visits in the first two months, then monthly or bi-monthly nursing visits, plus follow-up phone calls between visits. During a typical home visit, the Transitions nurse obtained an interim history of patients' symptoms, performs a brief physical assessment, and educated patients and caregivers about managing their symptoms, diet, medications, and activity, as well as the natural progression of their advanced HF. In usual care, all patients received a printed booklet for HF home management titled "A Stronger Pump" (Purcell & Johnston Fletcher, 2012).

Currently, all Transitions HF patients receive a one-page printed decision-support tool titled "Know when to call your nurse" (Appendix E). This handout features a list of signs and symptoms of HF exacerbation, which patients and caregivers are instructed to report to their Transitions nurse at any time. Transitions offers phone nurse support 24/7. Unlike the newly adapted HF zone tool to be evaluated in this EBP project, the current Transitions HF decision-support tool does not stratify HF signs and symptoms by their severity, nor does it sort these symptoms into green, yellow or red zones. After their 60-day post-implementation reassessment, participants in the control group received the HF zone tool and companion self-monitoring chart.

Intervention

For this EBP project, the PL and colleagues implemented the new Zones for HF Self-Management decision support tool (Appendix D-1) and companion chart (Appendix

D-2), in addition to usual Transitions care. Use of the HF zone tool and/or the "Know when to call your nurse" handout (Appendix E) was incorporated into the nurses' home visits. Transitions nurses provided the HF zone tool to participants in the intervention group. The nurses taught patients and caregivers how to use the new zone tool and companion chart to self-monitor and record their weight and symptoms daily.

Measurement Instruments

Newest Vital Sign

Upon enrollment in the pilot project, participants' health literacy (HL) was screened using the Newest Vital Sign (NVS) tool developed by Weiss et al. (2005) (Appendices F-1 & F-2). Distribution of the NVS, supported by Pfizer (2016), made the tool and instructions for its use and scoring by health professionals publicly available on its health literacy webpage. Written permission to use the NVS tool was obtained from Barry Weiss, the lead developer of the tool (Appendix F-3).

The NVS tool features six questions based on a nutrition content label for a fictitious type of ice cream (Appendix F-1). According the instructions in the online NVS toolkit, patients are given a copy of the nutrition label and are then asked the six questions orally by the administering professional, who records their answers and total scores (0-6 correct answers) on the printed NVS score sheets (Appendix F-2). This tool measures the ability to read, understand and analyze words (prose literacy), numbers (numeracy), and forms (document literacy) (Hubbard, 2011). On the NVS, a score of 0-1 suggests high likelihood (50% or more) of limited HL; a score of 2-3 indicates the possibility of limited HL, and a score of 4-6 almost always indicates adequate HL.

In their original study presenting the NVS tool, Weiss et al. (2005) analyzed and confirmed the instrument's internal consistency and criterion validity. Ramirez-Zohfeld et al. (2015) compared the performance of the NVS with another widely used HL tool, the Short Test of Functional Health Literacy in Adults (S-TOFHLA) among and between a sample of English and Spanish-speaking patients. They found that, in the full sample, the tests were moderately correlated ($r = 0.69, p < .0001$), with a stronger correlation among those completing the tests in Spanish ($r = 0.83, p < .0001$), as compared with those taking the tests in English ($r = 0.58, p < .0001$).

For participants with inadequate HL (NVS score of 0-1) or those who could not or chose not to complete the NVS test, the Transitions nurses screened their primary caregivers' HL using this tool after obtaining both the patients' and caregivers' written consent. If the caregiver's HL was adequate, then the Transitions nurses instructed the caregiver and patient in how to use the HF zone tool and its companion chart for daily self-monitoring of weight and HF symptoms. As previously noted, the adapted HF zone tool for this project was deliberately tailored to a low-literacy population.

Charlson Comorbidity Index

For this pilot EBP project, each participant's comorbidities were assessed by reviewing the patient's electronic health record (EHR). The burden of comorbidity was calculated with the Charlson Comorbidity Index, or CCI tool (Appendix G) (Charlson, Pompeii, Ales, & MacKenzie, 1987). The CCI is the most widely cited measure of comorbidity and risk of one-year mortality in clinical studies (de Groot, Beckerman, Lankhorst, & Bouter, 2003). Charlson et al. (1987) compiled a list of comorbid conditions whose relative risk of one-year mortality (following hospitalization) was 1.2

or greater, and assigned each condition a weighted score of 1 or greater, based on its adjusted risk of mortality. The weighted indices for each participant's comorbidities on the CCI list were added together to calculate total CCI score.

Validity and reliability of the CCI were originally established by Charlson et al. (1987) and later confirmed by Charlson, Szatrowski, Peterson, and Gold (1994) and de Groot et al. (2003). Self-reported CCI's predicted one-year mortality comparably with CCI's derived from administrative data (Chaudry, Jin, & Meltzer, 2005). Peterson, Paget, Lachs, Reid, and Charlson (2012) recommended ranking subjects' CCI scores into three risk ranges: 0-1 = low; 2-3 = moderate; 4 or greater = high.

Self-Care of Heart Failure Index

The Self-Care of Heart Failure Index (SCHFI v.6.2) (Appendix H-1) was used to measure participants' HF self-care pre- and post-intervention (Riegel, Lee, Dickson, & Carlson, 2009a; Riegel, 2015). If a participant was unable or chose not to complete the SCHFI tool, a relative completed a companion tool, the Caregiver Contribution to Self-Care of Heart Failure Index (CC-SCHFI) (Appendix H-2), which is available via the SCHFI website (Riegel, 2015). The original SCHFI tool was published by Riegel et al. (2004). The updated SCHFI v.6.2 was developed and validated by Riegel et al. (2009a).

Written permission for use of the SCHFI v.6.2 for this project was obtained from Dr. Barbara Riegel, the tool's lead developer (Appendix H-3). She indicated that the tool is in the public domain. The SCHFI v.6.2 is available online via the Self-Care of Heart Failure Index website (Riegel, 2015).

This most recent published version of the SCHFI includes 23 items, 22 with a four-point Likert scale and one yes/no question, grouped into three domains of HF self-

care: (1) Maintenance, (2) Management, and (3) Confidence. Each of these three subscales is scored 0-100, with higher scores indicating better self-care. A cut-point score of 70 is the minimum for adequate self-care. Riegel recommended that each of the subscales of the SCHFI v.6.2 be scored separately to rate patients' self-care in each of the three above-noted domains, but not to use a total self-care score for all three domains taken together (Riegel, 2015).

Cameron, Worrall-Carter, Driscoll, and Stewart (2009) reviewed 14 instruments that measure HF self-care. They found that the SCHFI was one of only two disease-specific measures of self-care that have undergone rigorous psychometric testing in HF populations. They found that the SCHFI demonstrated six aspects of validity and two of three aspects of reliability.

Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire

Participants' health-related quality of life (HRQoL) was measured pre- and post-intervention, using the short form of the Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire (KCCQ-12; Appendix I-1). Per John Spertus' emailed instructions (Appendix I-2), the PL obtained a license from CV Outcomes (Appendix I-3) with permission to use the KCCQ-12. Developed and validated by Spertus and Jones (2015), the KCCQ-12 is a shortened version of the 23-item Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire (KCCQ).

The original KCCQ was first presented and validated by Green, Porter, Bresnahan, and Spertus (2000). The KCCQ has been widely used, translated into several languages, and cited in dozens of studies assessing HRQoL in HF patients. In a systematic review of seven HF-specific HRQoL measurement tools, Garin et al. (2014)

identified the KCCQ overall as the most highly rated HF HRQoL instrument of all the tools that they analyzed.

The original 23-item KCCQ quantifies seven domains of HF-related health status: physical limitation (seven items), symptom stability (one item), symptom frequency (four items), symptom burden (three items), self-efficacy (two items), quality of life (three items), and social limitations (four items). Creber, Polomano, Farrar, and Riegel (2012) performed a secondary analysis of data from three studies to explore the original KCCQ's factor structure, evaluate this tool's reliability and validity, and determine the tool's most meaningful HRQoL components. They found good overall internal consistency reliability (Cronbach's alpha = .92) for the overall tool and subscales. There was high test-retest reliability (ICC > .81) for the KCCQ's social limitations, physical limitations and symptoms subscales, and moderate test-retest reliability (ICC = .66) for the self-efficacy subscale.

Spertus and Jones (2015) shortened the original KCCQ to a 12-item tool using 5- to 7-point Likert scales for participants to self-rate their HRQoL within 4 domains: physical limitation (3 items), symptom frequency (4 items), quality of life (2 items), and social limitation (3 items). Spertus and Jones also performed psychometric testing of the new KCCQ-12. Each of the items includes a 5- or 7-point Likert-type response rating severity of symptoms or frequency of limitations of various activities related to HF-specific HRQoL. Each subscale and the total instrument are scored from 0 to 100, with higher scores indicating better HRQoL (0 - <25 = Poor; 25 - <50 = Fair; 50 - <75 = Good; 75-100=Excellent). Using data from three clinical sites with 4168 subjects, they found a high correlation ($r > .93$) between the KCCQ-12 and the original 23-item KCCQ.

The KCCQ-12 showed high test-retest reliability ($r > .76$) for all domains. The KCCQ-12 also showed high responsiveness, prognostic significance, and clinical interpretability when compared with the original KCCQ.

Project Implementation and Data Collection

Enrollment and Pretesting of Participants

Prior to implementing this pilot project, the PL trained the Transitions nurses in use of the zone tool as well as the NVS, SCHFI v.6.2, CC-SCHFI, and KCCQ-12 tools. During a routine home visit, the nurses obtained patients' informed consent to participate in this project. The Transitions nurses screened for health literacy (HL) using the NVS tool. An NVS score of 2 or greater (out of a possible 6) was considered adequate HL for this pilot project.

If a patient could not or declined to complete the NVS due to visual impairment, low health literacy, or personal preference, the nurse obtained a relative's informed consent and administered the NVS to that relative. Among the fifteen original participants enrolled in this project, only five completed their own measurement instruments. For the other ten participants, their relatives completed the NVS and other measurement tools. Next, participants or their relatives completed pretests with the SCHFI v.6.2 or CC-SCHFI, and then the KCCQ-12, to measure the outcomes of interest at baseline (Project Goal 2, Objective a).

After administering these pretests, the nurses began implementing the HF zone tool plus usual care with participants and/or caregivers in the intervention group (project goal #1) or usual care with the control group. Nurses instructed participants in use of the new zone tool and/or current "Know when to call your nurse" handout to help guide their

daily HF self-monitoring. These decision-support tools helped participants recognize when they needed to report worsening HF symptoms to their Transitions nurse.

Posttesting of Participants

One month (25-35 days) and two months (55-65 days) after enrollment in the project, the nurses administered posttests with the SCHFI v.6.2 or CC-SCHFI and the KCCQ-12. The outcomes of interest, HF self-care and HF-related quality of life, were thus measured a total of three times (project goal #2, objective b). At the two-month post-test visits, the nurses asked participants or their relatives to complete a brief survey (Appendices J-1 & J-2) to provide feedback about the zone tool and/or printed HF handout, the three measurement tools, and the project in general.

Data Entry

Participants' demographic data (age, gender, race, number of months on Transitions, presence or absence of primary caregiver) and co-morbidities were extracted from their electronic medical records and entered into an Excel document. Participants' scores on the NVS, CCI, SCHFI v.6.2 or CC-SCHFI, and KCCQ-12) were entered into Excel documents by the PL. All digital data for this project were stored in the password-protected laptop computers of the PL, project chair, and statistician/co-chair. These data were then transferred into a dataset using IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software (IBM SPSS Statistics, v.23, 2015). All data were coded in SPSS using distinct variable names for further analysis.

Data Analysis

The resulting electronic dataset was examined for data-entry errors and missing scores. Missing scores were re-coded using SPSS to avoid skewing the mean scores obtained from the measurement tools. Histograms of the scores for each variable were examined for

any extreme outlying scores that could be due to scoring errors by the PL. Descriptive statistics were generated on participants' demographic variables, and scores on the CCI, NVS, SCHFI v.6.2 or CC-SCHFI, and KCCQ-12 instruments.

Demographic data (months on Transitions, age, gender, race, CCI raw score; CCI category; NVS raw score; NVS category, caregiver status, and who reported data) were analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) or Spearman's rho for associations with Pretest to Posttest 1 changes in HF self-care and HF QoL, the primary outcomes of interest (Project Goal 3). In order to evaluate the HF zone tool's effect on HF self-care and HF-related QoL (Project Goal 2, Objective c), a series of 8 repeated-measures ANOVA tests was conducted to determine whether these outcomes of interest changed significantly from Pretest to 1-month and 2-months Posttest on these measures:

1. Self-Care of Heart Failure Index (SCHFI v.6.2 or CC-SCHFI): Maintenance Subscale
2. SCHFI v.6.2 or CC-SCHFI: Management Subscale
3. SCHFI v.6.2 or CC-SCHFI: Confidence Subscale
4. Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire (KCCQ-12): Physical Limitation Subscale
5. KCCQ-12: Symptom Frequency Subscale
6. KCCQ-12: Quality of Life Subscale
7. KCCQ-12: Social Limitation Subscale
8. KCCQ-12: Summary Score

Post-implementation Participant and Nurse Surveys

After completing Posttest 2, the participants were asked to complete a brief survey for the control group (Appendix J-1) or intervention group (Appendix J-2) to rate

the zone tool's and/or usual handout's ease of reading and helpfulness for monitoring and responding to their HF symptoms (Project Goal 4). This survey also asked participants to rate ease of understanding and completion of the NVS, SCHFI, and KCCQ-12 measurement tools (Project Goal 5). Participant surveys used questions with five-point Likert scales for rating of the above-noted tools. A series of independent-samples t-tests compared the mean ratings of these tools between the Intervention and Control groups. Three open-ended questions also elicited participants' subjective feedback about this pilot project and any suggestions for improving the project process. Themes were identified for participants' responses to these open-ended qualitative questions.

For Project Goals 4 and 5, the Transitions nurses were also asked at the conclusion of this pilot project to complete a brief survey (Appendix J-3). The survey used 5-point Likert scales for nurses to rate the ease of understanding and helpfulness of the "Know when to call your nurse" handout (usual care) and the new HF zone tool (intervention), and the ease of understanding and completion of the NVS, SCHFI and KCCQ-12 tools. Additionally, the nurses were asked three open-ended questions in this survey to elicit their suggestions for improving the overall project. Themes were identified for nurses' responses to these open-ended qualitative questions.

RESULTS

Participant Demographics

For this pilot EBP project, the PL and two nurse colleagues recruited and enrolled fifteen participants from the population of Transitions patients with a primary diagnosis of heart failure. This sample constituted about one third of the recent average total census of Transitions HF patients. A random number generator website (random.org there are many tools on this website. Use the correct format for the specific item used in the citation and reference) was used to randomize eight participants to the Intervention group and seven to the Control group.

Shortly after enrollment, there was attrition of one participant in the control group due to admission to home hospice care with a diagnosis of end-stage HF. The remaining fourteen participants all completed Posttest 1 at approximately 30 days' and Posttest 2 at approximately 60 days' post-enrollment. Data collection began on November 11, 2016 and concluded on February 16, 2017.

Table 1 summarizes the demographics of the Intervention and Control patients and of the combined sample. As this table shows, few statistically significant, substantive differences between Intervention and Control subjects emerged. There was a significant difference between the Intervention and Control group for the CCI Risk Category, with 85.7% of the Control group vs. 25% of the Intervention group in the highest comorbidity risk category. Also, the Control group's average age (90) and months on the Transitions program (11.4) were greater than those of the Intervention group (85; 4.3), but these differences were not statistically significant. Another point of interest was that only five of the enrolled participants completed their own measurement tools, while

the other ten deferred to a relative/caregiver to complete these tools. This was most likely due to participants' advanced age, physical frailty, and/or mild cognitive impairment.

Correlations between Demographic Factors and Outcomes of Interest

For Project Goal 3, demographic factors were analyzed for correlations with the outcomes of interest, HF self-care and quality of life. In Table 2, three demographic factors showed statistically significant correlations with particular subscales of the SCHFI or KCCQ-12:

1. There was a strong negative correlation between CCI Raw Score and SCHFI Management. As CCI raw scores increased (indicating a greater burden of comorbidity), self-care management scores decreased (and vice-versa).
2. As CCI Risk category scores increased (indicating a more severe risk of hospitalization due to greater comorbidity), self-care management scores decreased (and vice-versa).
3. Also, there was a strong positive correlation between gender and KCCQ-12 Social Limitation scores; females showed higher scores on the Social Limitation subscale, indicating they reported a lesser extent of social limitation than did males.

Table 1

Participant Demographics (n = 15)

Demographic	Intervention Group (n = 8)		Control Group (n = 7)		Combined (n = 15)		Effect Size ^a	<i>p</i> ^b
	Mean (SD)	Freq. (Valid %)	Mean (SD)	Freq. (Valid %)	Mean (SD)	Freq. (Valid %)		
Months in Program	4.3 (3.6)		11.4 (12.8)		7.6 (9.5)		.76	.15
Age	85.0 (7.0)		90.0 (5.8)		87.3 (6.8)		.78	.16
Gender							.20	.45
Male		3 (37.5)		4 (57.1)		7 (46.7)		
Female		5 (62.5)		3 (42.9)		8 (53.3)		
Race							.37	.56
African American		1 (12.5)		1 (14.3)		2 (13.3)		
Asian		2 (25.0)		0		2 (13.3)		
Hispanic		1 (12.5)		1 (14.3)		2 (13.3)		
White		4 (50.0)		5 (71.4)		9 (60.0)		
CCI, Raw Score	3.3 (2.2)		4.3 (1.8)		3.7 (2.0)		.45	.34
CCI, Risk Category							.65	.04
Low		2 (25.0)		1 (14.3)		3 (20.0)		
Moderate		4 (50.0)		0		4 (26.7)		
High		2 (25.0)		6 (85.7)		8 (53.3)		
NVS, Raw Score	4.6 (1.4)		4.1 (0.9)		4.4 (1.2)		.42	.45
NVS, Literacy Category							.20	.44
High Possibility of Limited Literacy		0		0		0		
Possible Limited Literacy		1 (12.5)		2 (28.6)		3 (20.0)		
Adequate Literacy		7 (87.5)		5 (71.4)		12 (80.0)		
Caregiver Status							.45	.22
Full-time		5 (62.5)		4 (57.1)		9 (60.0)		
Part-time		1 (12.5)		3 (42.9)		4 (26.7)		
No Caregiver		2 (25.0)		0		2 (13.3)		
Data Reported By							-.09	.71
Patient		3 (37.5)		2 (28.6)		5 (33.3)		
Caregiver		5 (62.5)		5 (71.4)		10 (66.7)		

^a Cohen's D (for Independent Samples t-tests) and Cramér's V (for Chi-Square Tests of Independence) or Phi (for 2x2 Chi-Square Tests of Independence)

^b Reported for Independent Samples t-tests (numeric variables) and Chi-Square Tests of Independence (categorical variables)

CCI=Charlson Comorbidity Index; NVS=Newest Vital Sign

Table 2

Correlation Matrix of Patient Demographics and Changes in Scores from Pretest to Posttest 1

	SCHFI			KCCQ-12				
	Maintenance	Management	Confidence	Physical Limitation	Symptom Frequency	Quality of Life	Social Limitation	KCCQ12 Summary
Months in Program	-.08	-.40	.03	-.05	-.25	-.11	.25	-.12
Age	-.15	-.08	.15	-.66	.09	-.35	-.12	-.28
Gender ^a	.38	.16	.08	-.004	.30	< .001	.71*	.21
Race ^b	.26	.33	-.08	.61	.20	< .001	.16	.46
CCI, Raw Score	-.37	-.79**	-.23	.41	-.07	.18	-.57	.15
CCI, Category [‡]	-.45	-.86***	.06	.38	-.15	.33	-.21	.24
NVS, Raw Score	.11	.16	.06	-.23	-.19	.08	.52	-.03
NVS, Category [‡]	.41	^c	-.49	-.21	-.02	-.07	.40	.02
Caregiver Status ^c	.01	.34	-.08	-.42	-.06	.28	-.43	-.38
Data Reported By ^f	.29	.10	.07	.01	.18	-.47	.26	.09

Reference Categories = a: Male, b: White, c: Full-Time, d: Patient

[‡] indicates Spearman's rho used instead of Pearson's

* $p \leq .05$, ** $p \leq .01$, *** $p \leq .001$

^c No correlation could be calculated, as one of the measures was a constant

Effect of Zone Tool on Heart Failure Self-Care

Table 3 shows the Intervention and Control groups' baseline (pretest) scores on the three SCHFI subscales and the four KCCQ-12 subscales and KCCQ-12 summary scores. In order to determine the effect of implementing the new Zone Tool on participants' SCHFI subscale scores, a series of 2 x 3 repeated measures ANOVA's was conducted. These analyses examined the effects of Condition (Intervention vs. Control), Time (Pretest vs. 30-day Posttest vs. 60-day Posttest), and the interaction of Condition and Time. Success of the Zone Tool intervention would be indicated by a data pattern showing a significant interaction between Condition and Time, i.e. the intervention group participants' scores would improve over time while control group participants' scores would remain stable, deteriorate over time, or increase at a lesser rate over time.

Table 3

Summary of Independent Samples t-tests Comparing Intervention and Control Groups' Baseline Subscale Scores

Subscale	Mean Score		<i>p</i>
	Intervention	Control	
SCHFI Maintenance	76.13	74.42	.76
SCHFI Management	44.17	72.00	.18
SCHFI Confidence	58.42	67.57	.37
KCCQ-12 Physical Limitation	53.13	47.50	.78
KCCQ-12 Symptom Frequency	63.54	68.45	.65
KCCQ-12 Quality of Life	57.81	60.71	.79
KCCQ-12 Social Limitation	41.67	61.11	.34
KCCQ-12 Summary	54.95	61.46	.59

Due to the small sample size of this pilot study, it was anticipated that these analyses would not reach statistical significance at the $p < .05$ level. Instead, for each subscale, it was decided to examine the distribution of mean scores for Intervention and Control participants over time to determine whether or not a *post hoc* power analysis would be warranted. As shown in Figures 2-4, for all three SCHFI subscales, the anticipated pattern of data was not present, so power analyses were not conducted.

SCHFI Maintenance Subscale

The mean HF self-care maintenance Pretest, Posttest 1, and Posttest 2 scores for the Intervention and Control groups are displayed in Figure 2. When the SCHFI Maintenance subscale was examined, the 2 x 3 repeated measures ANOVA failed to detect a statistically significant interaction between time and condition ($F_{(2,24)} = 2.69$, $p = .09$, $\eta p^2 = .18$).

Figure 2. Distribution of mean SCHFI maintenance scores by condition and time ($n = 14$).

SCHFI Management Subscale

Mean SCHFI Management Pretest and Posttest scores for both groups are shown in Figure 3. When this subscale was examined, the 2 x 3 repeated measures ANOVA failed to detect a statistically significant interaction between time and condition ($F_{(2,14)} = 0.99, p = .40, \eta p^2 = .12$).

Figure 3. Distribution of mean SCHFI management scores by condition and time ($n = 9$).

SCHFI Confidence Subscale

The mean SCHFI Confidence subscale Pretest and Posttest scores for Intervention and Control groups are depicted in Figure 4. When this subscale was examined, the 2 x 3 repeated measures ANOVA failed to detect a statistically significant interaction between time and condition ($F_{(2,22)} = 2.74, p = .09, \eta p^2 = .20$).

Figure 4. Distribution of mean SCHFI confidence scores by condition and time ($n = 13$).

Effect of Zone Tool on HF-Related Quality of Life

In order to determine whether implementation of a Zone Tool would impact participants' scores on the four KCCQ-12 subscales and the KCCQ-12 Summary scale, a series of 2 x 3 repeated measures ANOVA's was conducted to examine the effect of Condition (Zone Tool vs. control), Time (Pretest vs. 30-day Posttest vs. 60-day Posttest), and the interaction of Condition and Time. Success of the Zone Tool intervention would be indicated by a significant interaction between Condition and Time, with a data pattern showing that participants in the Zone Tool condition's scores improved over time while control group participants' scores remained stable, deteriorated over time, or increased at a lesser rate over time.

Due to the small sample size of this pilot study, it was anticipated that the analyses would not reach statistical significance at the $p = 0.05$ level. Instead, it was decided to examine the distribution of mean scores for Intervention and Control participants over time to determine whether *post hoc* power analyses were warranted. For all four KCCQ-12 subscales and the KCCQ-12 summary scale, the anticipated pattern of data was not present, so power analyses were not conducted.

KCCQ-12: Physical Limitation Subscale

Mean KCCQ-12 Physical Limitation Pretest and Posttest scores for both groups are shown in Figure 5. When this subscale was examined, the 2 x 3 repeated measures ANOVA failed to detect a statistically significant interaction between time and condition ($F_{(2,10)} = 0.55, p = .59, \eta p^2 = .10$).

Figure 5. Distribution of mean KCCQ-12 physical limitation scores by condition & time ($n = 7$).

KCCQ-12: Symptom Frequency Subscale

Mean KCCQ-12 Symptom Frequency Pretest and Posttest scores for both groups are shown in Figure 6. When this subscale was examined, the 2 x 3 repeated measures ANOVA failed to detect a statistically significant interaction between time and condition ($F_{(2,24)} = 0.41, p = .67, \eta p^2 = .03$).

Figure 6. Distribution of mean KCCQ-12 symptom frequency scores by condition & time (n = 14).

KCCQ-12: Quality of Life Subscale

Mean KCCQ-12 Quality of Life Pretest and Posttest scores for both groups are shown in Figure 7. When this subscale was examined, the 2 x 3 repeated measures ANOVA failed to detect a statistically significant interaction between time and condition ($F_{(2,24)} = 0.98, p = .39, \eta^2 = .08$).

Figure 7. Distribution of mean KCCQ-12 quality of life scores by condition & time ($n = 14$).

KCCQ-12: Social Limitation Subscale

Mean KCCQ-12 Social Limitation Pretest and Posttest scores for both groups are shown in Figure 8. When this subscale was examined, the 2 x 3 repeated measures ANOVA failed to detect a statistically significant interaction between time and condition ($F_{(2,10)} = 1.12, p = .36, \eta p^2 = .18$).

Figure 8. Distribution of mean KCCQ12 social limitation scores by condition & time ($n = 7$).

KCCQ-12: Summary Score

Mean KCCQ-12 Summary Pretest and Posttest scores for both groups are shown in Figure 9. When these scores were examined, the 2 x 3 repeated measures ANOVA failed to detect a statistically significant interaction between time and condition ($F_{(2,24)} = 0.92, p = .41, \eta p^2 = .07$).

Figure 9. Distribution of mean KCCQ-12 summary scores by condition & time ($n = 14$).

Discussion of Findings for Outcomes of Interest

As previously stated, the purpose of this pilot project was to evaluate the effect of the HF zone tool on two primary outcomes of interest, HF self-care and quality of life. Nearly all of the SCHFI and KCCQ-12 subscales showed some increase in the Intervention group's mean scores from Pretest to Posttest 1 and then some decrease in this group's scores from Posttest 1 to Posttest 2. The one notable exception was in the KCCQ-12 Quality of Life subscale (Figure 7), for which the Intervention group showed decreased mean scores from Pretest to Posttest 1 and further decrease to Posttest 2. At this point, however, it is not appropriate to ascribe a pattern of "directions" in the data, as there is no evidence to conclude that these fluctuations were not a result of chance alone.

None of the eight repeated-measures ANOVA's detected a statistically significant interaction between time and condition. These results failed to support the hypothesis that zone tool plus usual care was more effective than usual care alone in improving HF self-care or HF-related quality of life. A much larger sample with more data points would be more likely to yield results that could demonstrate whether or not use of the zone tool has a significant effect on HF self-care and HF-related quality of life.

Post-Implementation Surveys

Participants' Survey Results

The fourteen project participants who completed both posttests also completed a post-implementation survey (Appendices J-1 and J-2), which the author had created to elicit their feedback on different elements of this project. Table 4 presents participants' average ratings (on five-point Likert scales) of the ease of understanding and helpfulness of the usual care decision-support handout and the zone tool for HF self-management, as

well as the ease of understanding and completion of the NVS, SCHFI, and KCCQ-12.

The survey results indicate that participants in both groups rated the usual care HF decision-support tool and the new HF zone tool as somewhat easy to understand and somewhat helpful in enabling them to recognize signs and symptoms of HF exacerbation. Except for the Control group's rating of the KCCQ-12, both groups found all three measurement tools used in this project somewhat easy to understand and complete.

Table 4

Summary of Independent Samples t-tests Comparing Participant Survey Scores

	Mean rating (1-5 scale) (<i>SD</i>)		
	Intervention	Control	<i>p</i>
"Know When to Call Nurse" Tool: Ease of understanding	4.00 (0.58)	4.00 (0.89)	1.00
"Know When to Call Nurse" Tool: Helpfulness	4.43 (0.54)	4.67 (0.52)	.43
HF Zone Tool: Ease of Understanding	4.14 (1.07)	*	-
HF Zone Tool: Helpfulness	4.29 (0.48)	*	-
NVS: Ease of Understanding & Completion	4.29 (0.76)	4.17 (1.17)	.83
SCHFI: Ease of Understanding & Completion	4.13 (0.84)	4.50 (0.55)	.36
KCCQ-12: Ease of Understanding & Completion	4.13 (0.84)	3.83 (0.75)	.51

* Control group did not receive HF Zone Tool

The participants were also asked three-open ended questions regarding what they liked or disliked about participating in this research project and any suggestions they had for improving the project. Two positive themes were noted in their responses to the

open-ended question regarding what they liked about this EBP project: (a) Participating in this project helped them be more aware of their HF and their health, and (b) people who received the HF zone tool also said it helped them to recognize the signs and symptoms of HF exacerbation. Some aspects of this project that participants disliked were: (a) taking time to complete the measurement tools or complete the daily self-checkup form, (b) ambiguity of certain questions on the CC-SCHFI for one patient who had multiple caregivers, and (c) lack of space on the daily self-monitoring form to record patient's blood pressure and pulse. Suggestions for improving the project were: (a) simplify the measurement tools' questions, (b) add columns on the self-monitoring form to record pulse and blood pressure, and (c) modify the measurement tools for use with patients living in facilities with multiple caregivers.

Nurses' Survey Results

The two Transitions nurses who helped with enrolling participants and collecting data completed a post-implementation survey (see Appendix J-3) designed by the PL, with quantitative and qualitative questions very similar to those in the participant survey. One nurse rated the two decision-support tools as very easy to understand and very helpful and two of the three measurement tools as somewhat easy to understand and complete. The other nurse considered the new zone tool to be somewhat hard to understand and somewhat helpful, and two of the three measurement tools as somewhat hard to understand and complete. Both nurses liked that the new HF zone tool helped their patients learn about and understand which signs and symptoms of HF needed to be reported to the nurse, and both disliked that conducting the data collection increased the length of their home visits. The nurses' suggestions for improving the project were:

(a) have one nurse conduct the project to ensure uniformity of patient teaching, (b) allow more time for the duration of the project, and (c) work with the Transitions supervisor to adjust the nurses' productivity expectations on days when they devote extra work time to assisting with this research.

Project Limitations

While the data analysis did not demonstrate a significant effect of the zone tool intervention on HF self-care or quality of life, this is attributable in part to several methodological limitations. First, the pilot project's small sample size severely limited generalizability, raised concerns about Type II errors, and instilled doubts about the validity of the Intervention and Control group means for nearly all the findings. The sample size was limited by the total Transitions HF patient census averaging 40-45 patients and by an unanticipated shortage of time for nurses to enroll and survey participants. This was partly due to the lengthy project review and approval process by two Sharp research entities and the CSU Fullerton IRB, which spanned nearly four months. Another unforeseen development was fewer than expected nurses available to help with the project due to parenting leave and staff turnover, which further limited the time available to enroll participants and complete data collection.

Another limiting factor was the nature of some of the well-validated KCCQ-12 instrument's questions. This tool asks patients to rate how severely their HF limits their ability to do particular activities, such as "walking one block on level ground" and "hurrying or jogging (as if to catch a bus)" and "hobbies, recreational activities" and "working or doing household chores". Some of these questions did not apply to several of these frail elderly participants, who no longer perform some of these activities. The KCCQ-12 offers an option to select "limited for other reasons or did not do this activity

or "does not apply or did not do for other reasons". These responses are scored as missing values on the KCCQ-12 scoring instructions, which limited the sub-sample sizes ($n = 7$) for the Physical Limitation and Social Limitation subscales.

IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE

This EBP pilot project demonstrated the feasibility of developing and implementing a zone tool for HF self-management for patients with advanced HF in a home-based palliative care (PC) program. This zone tool helped participants become more aware of their HF and the signs/symptoms of HF exacerbation to report to their nurse. The Transitions nurses were able to use the SCHFI or CC-SCHFI to measure participants HF self-care or caregiver contributions to patients' HF self-care, as well as the KCCQ-12 to measure HF-related quality of life. Since the KCCQ-12 was found to be a less than optimal tool for measuring QoL, future EBP research should utilize a different quantitative tool or perhaps a mixed-methods approach to assess participants' QoL in this PC population.

Post-implementation surveys helped the author to evaluate participants' and nurses' ratings of the zone tool and usual care decision-support tool, as well as the measurement instruments. Participants appreciated the opportunity to participate in this EBP project focused on HF self-care and quality of life, and they found the measurement tools somewhat easy to understand and complete. In future research, these surveys should include follow-up questions for participants and nurses to clarify or elaborate on their ratings of these tools.

By their limited nature and scope, pilot studies usually feature small sample sizes to test the feasibility of particular interventions and research methods, which this project did accomplish. Due to this project's small sample size, it was not possible to determine if the results were due to the intervention or to chance alone. In order to determine if the zone tool can have a significant effect on HF self-care and HF-related quality of life,

additional research is recommended with a larger sample and more data points. To more accurately assess quality of life in these frail, elderly PC patients, future research should utilize a different QoL measurement tool or a mixed-methods approach that is better suited to this population.

In the conceptual framework for this project, HF symptom perception helps to mediate the relationship between self-care maintenance and self-care management. The developers of the Self-care of Heart Failure Index, which is based on this framework, are validating an updated version of this tool that will measure HF symptom perception as well as self-care maintenance and self-care management. Current research literature supports the effectiveness of palliative care and self-care interventions in general and programs featuring green-yellow-red zone tools in particular in reducing hospitalizations and healthcare costs. Evidence is still lacking on the effect of zone-tool interventions on HF self-care and quality of life as primary outcomes of interest. Therefore, this pilot project points to a need for future larger-scale research that evaluates zone tool-based interventions' impact on HF patients' self-care and quality of life.

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APPENDIX A-1

REVIEW/APPROVAL FOR PROJECT FROM SHARP GROSSMONT
INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH EBP COMMITTEE

IREBPC Study/Project Review Rubric

Name: Daniel Weiss

Study Title: Pilot Study of a Low-literacy Zone Tool for Heart Failure Self-management

Please provide feedback about the study by checking the box that best fits your assessment of the study and providing comments below.			
Significance	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Significance clearly identifies need for study.	<input type="checkbox"/> Significance to support need for the study not clear	<input type="checkbox"/> background to support need for the study
Background	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Background clearly identifies need for study. Literature cited is pertinent and timely.	<input type="checkbox"/> Background to support need for the study not clear. Literature review lacks pertinence or is outdated.	<input type="checkbox"/> Limited background to support need for the study. Literature review lacks pertinence and is outdated
Purpose or Aim of project	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clear purpose strongly aligned with SHC priorities; will benefit/advance patient care and nursing practice.	<input type="checkbox"/> Study purpose somewhat clear and/or will benefit patients or nursing practice.	<input type="checkbox"/> Purpose not clear and/or not aligned with SHC priorities; will not benefit patients or nursing practice.
Research Question/PICO	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clear research question/ PICO question.		<input type="checkbox"/> Study Research Question/PICO not clear.
Theoretical Framework and/or EBP Model of project (if applicable)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Theoretical and/or EBP model framework, rationale, and/or map, is appropriate. Key concepts are adequately defined conceptually.	<input type="checkbox"/> Theoretical and/or EBP model framework, rationale, and/or map, is not clear or appropriate. Key concepts are not clearly defined conceptually.	<input type="checkbox"/> Theoretical and/or EBP model framework, rationale, and/or map, is not addressed and project would benefit by addressing this area.
Research Methodology			
Study Design	<input type="checkbox"/> Design or methodology is appropriate for study question/s.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design or methodology needs to be revised to be appropriate for study question/s.	<input type="checkbox"/> Design or methodology is not appropriate for study question/s.
Population & Sample	<input type="checkbox"/> Sample very appropriate in size and selection. Plans to recruit and retain subjects are very clear and feasible.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sample size and selection fairly well considered. Plans to recruit and retain subjects are fairly clear and/or feasible.	<input type="checkbox"/> Sample size and selection not well considered. Plans to recruit and retain subjects are not clear or feasible.
Measures/Instruments/Survey/Tools	<input type="checkbox"/> Approaches to enhance credibility and trustworthiness and/or use of instruments with acceptable reliability and validity are very clearly described.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Approaches to enhance credibility and trustworthiness and/or use of instruments with acceptable reliability and validity are fairly clear.	<input type="checkbox"/> Approaches to enhance credibility and trustworthiness and/or use of instruments with acceptable reliability and validity are poorly described.
Protection of Human Subjects <i>N/A for projects that are not Human Subject Research or Human Subject Research but Exempt.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Procedures to protect human subjects and seek IRB approval very well described or lack thereof clearly justified	<input type="checkbox"/> Procedures to protect human subjects and seek IRB approval fairly well described or lack thereof somewhat justified <i>This project tends to be leaning toward human subject research and will need to go through IRB.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Procedures to protect human subjects and seek IRB approval poorly described or lack thereof poorly justified

IREBPC Study/Project Review Rubric

Data Collection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plans for data collection protocol is clear, feasible and methodologically rigorous	<input type="checkbox"/> Plans for data collection protocol is fairly clear, feasible and rigorous	<input type="checkbox"/> Plans for data collection protocol lacks clarity, feasibility or rigor
Data Analysis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plans for Analysis very appropriate to method, study question(s), and demonstrate high level of rigor	<input type="checkbox"/> Plans for Analysis fairly appropriate to method, study question(s), but demonstrate limited rigor	<input type="checkbox"/> Plans for Analysis not appropriate to method and/or study question(s), demonstrating very limited rigor
Results	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Study outcomes are clearly stated and are reflective of improvements patient care and nursing practice.	<input type="checkbox"/> Study outcomes are fairly stated and/or may be reflective of improvements patient care and nursing practice.	<input type="checkbox"/> Study outcomes are not stated and/or are not reflective of improvements patient care and nursing practice.
Plans for Dissemination	<input type="checkbox"/> Appropriate and well described	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Somewhat a appropriate and described	<input type="checkbox"/> Poor appropriateness and description
Resources Needed/Costs	<input type="checkbox"/> Resources needed and costs that could be incurred clearly stated. Support for resources and costs identified.	<input type="checkbox"/> Resources needed and costs that could be incurred not clearly stated. Support for resources and costs not clearly identified.	<input type="checkbox"/> Resources needed and costs that could be incurred not stated. Support for resources and costs not identified.
Research's Experience:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researcher's experience level is adequate to support project no further support needed.	<input type="checkbox"/> Researcher's experience level is limited to support project and additional support/mentor is recommended. <i>Support Suggested for IRB process and approval process through Sharp Healthcare.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Researcher's does not have research Experience to support project and additional support/mentor is highly recommended.
Clarity of writing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Well written, jargon-free, no typographical and grammatical errors	<input type="checkbox"/> Fairly well written, jargon-free, multiple typographical and grammatical errors	<input type="checkbox"/> Poorly written; many typographical and grammatical errors
<p>Comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is xxx a very well put together project and presented very well. The following are suggestions from the Sharp Grossmont IREBP committee: Would like more information on validity of instruments chosen in this project written in project write up. PICO question refers to "usual care", would make a statement in project write up what "usual care" is currently. Inclusion and exclusion criteria of population and sample is unclear. Statement was made in presentation that may have caregiver fill out pre and posttest. If so, the caregiver will need to be identified within your population or sample. Also any other tools that are specified for the caregiver vs the patient will need to be included in write-up. How will a patient be chosen to be included in control group vs. intervention group? If you are including Spanish speaking or any other patient/caregiver speaking other than English will need to include this in inclusion or exclusion criteria. Also, all tools in English and the different languages will need to be submitted in Appendix. An overlap in a current Heart failure study will occur if Sharp Grossmont Hospital patients are included in this project and suggestions have been made to exclude patients discharged from Sharp Grossmont Hospital. Please contact Willa Fields and Colleen Austel-Nadeau for exact wording on how to avoid this from happening. <p>Recommended that this project be reviewed by SHC Research Council and go through IRB process as this project appears to be human subject's research involved. Please Contact Ana-Maria Gallo to help mentor through the IRB process.</p>			

APPENDIX A-2

PROJECT APPROVAL LETTER FROM SHARP HEALTH CARE
NURSING RESEARCH AND EVIDENCE-BASED PRACTICE COMMITTEE

Date: September 9, 2016

To: Dan Weiss, RN

From: Caroline Etland, PhD, RN
Chair, Sharp System Nursing Research and Evidence-Based Practice Committee

Re: Pilot Implementation of a Low-Literacy Zone Tool for Heart Failure Self-Management Project

Dear Mr. Weiss,

I am pleased to communicate that your proposal for an evidence-based practice project entitled, "Pilot Implementation of a Low-Literacy Zone Tool for Heart Failure Self-Management" has been approved by the Sharp Health Care system Nursing Research and Evidence-Based Practice Committee.

At the August 19, 2016 meeting it was agreed that the proposed project did not constitute human subjects research (HSR) and that the study activities could proceed. Additional modifications to the project design, data collected, forms and/or project personnel should be communicated to the Sharp Grossmont Hospital Director of Education, Research and Professional Practice, Dr. Gallo, prior to any change being implemented.

This communication serves as internal Sharp approval to conduct your project within the Sharp Hospice Transitions Palliative Care Heart Failure program. Please ensure that project results are presented to Dr. Gallo at the conclusion of your project, and prior to external dissemination. We wish you a smooth journey in the conduct of your valuable project.

Warm Regards,

Caroline Etland
Chair, Sharp Health Care Nursing Research and Evidence-Based Practice Committee.

APPENDIX A-3**EMAIL CORRESPONDENCE BETWEEN DNP PROJECT CHAIR
AND SHARP RESEARCH COMMITTEE CHAIR
RE: INFORMED CONSENT REQUIREMENT**

From: Caroline Etland [Caroline.Etland@sharp.com]
Sent: Wednesday, September 21, 2016 2:16 PM
To: Robertson, Suzanne
Subject: RE: Dan Weiss' project

Hi Sue, I spoke with our IRB member and Dan is OK to get a consent signed using the CSU Fullerton template. Let me know if there is anything else we can do to help him.

Caroline Etland, PhD, RN, AOCN, ACHPN
Director of Education, Research & Professional Practice
Sharp Chula Vista Medical Center
[619-502-3054](tel:619-502-3054)

From: Robertson, Suzanne [srobertson@Exchange.FULLERTON.EDU]
Sent: Wednesday, September 21, 2016 9:42 AM
To: Caroline Etland
Cc: sue robertson
Subject: Dan Weiss' project

Hi, Caroline. You and I spoke a week ago about the CSUF IRB requirement that Dan obtain written consent from his participants. Were you able to speak with the Sharp IRB? We are anxious to move forward with implementation.
Best regards,
Sue

Sue Robertson, RN, PhD, CNE
Associate Professor
Coordinator, Nurse Educator Concentration
Cal State Fullerton | School of Nursing

APPENDIX A-4

PROJECT APPROVAL NOTICE FROM CSU FULLERTON IRB

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research Development

P.O. Box 9850 at 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd, Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7540 / F 657-278-7236

APPROVAL NOTICEFrom the Institutional Review Board
California State University Fullerton

Date: **October 28, 2016**

From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chairperson *MCE*
CSUF Institutional Review Board

To: **Daniel J. Weiss**

Department: **Nursing**

Re: **Use of Human Subjects in Research Project entitled:
Pilot Implementation of a Low-Literacy Zone Tool for Heart Failure Self-management**

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human subjects in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University Fullerton, Institutional Review Board ("CSUF IRB"). Your proposal is determined to be Expedited per 45 CFR § 46.110(f).

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

If the above-referenced project has not been completed by **October 27, 2017** you must request renewed approval for continuation of the proposal.

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participation and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires resubmission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation. Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-referenced title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any change in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chairman of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that s/he is responsible for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

This institution has an Assurance on file with the Office for Human Research Protections.
The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: Dr. Sue Robertson
Application No. HSR-16-0354

APPENDIX B

INFORMED CONSENT LETTER

Informed Consent

Dear:

My name is Dan Weiss, RN, MS, CHPN. I am a clinical nurse at Sharp Transitions Program and a doctoral student under the direction of Sue Robertson, RN, PhD, CNE, Associate Professor at California State University, Fullerton School of Nursing.

I am conducting an evidence-based practice pilot project to examine the effect of a heart failure decision support tool on self-care and quality of life. For this project, we will be asking participants to complete 2 surveys, one on heart failure self-care behaviors (23 questions) and one on heart failure related quality of life (12 questions). This will help us to learn whether or not this decision support tool affects people's self-care and quality of life.

Participants will be asked to complete these 2 printed surveys when they first enroll in the project and then after about 30 days and 60 days. The 2 surveys ask you to rate (on a 4-point or 6-point scale) how often you do certain self-care behaviors or how much your heart failure affects your ability to do a few specific activities. When beginning in this project, participants will also be given a 6-question test of health literacy based on reading a nutrition label.

Your participation will involve completing these 2 printed surveys with pencil on paper (which takes a total of 15-20 minutes) during 3 home visits by your Transitions nurse, each about a month apart. At the first of these 3 visits, your nurse will also ask you 6 questions related to reading a nutrition label. The only possible risk from completing this test and these surveys may be some mental stress if you are uncomfortable answering the questions. If you do not feel comfortable answering any of the questions on these 2 printed surveys or the 1 oral test, you do not have to answer the question.

To protect your privacy, you will receive a unique ID number only for this project, which will be different from your Transitions or Sharp medical record numbers. Your name and other identifying information will not be shown on your survey forms. Survey responses will be combined to avoid identifying individual participants. Your survey forms will be kept in locked storage in the Transitions office, and your answers will be entered into secure files on the researchers' password-protected computers. Research records will be kept confidential to the extent allowed by law. Tests and surveys will be shredded at the end of the project.

Your participation in this project is voluntary, and you are free to withdraw from participation at any time without affecting your care from the Transitions program. If you leave this project for any reason, you will not suffer any penalty or loss of benefits or services to which you may otherwise be entitled. You will not be compensated (paid) in any way for volunteering to participate in this project.

If you have questions about this project, please contact Dan Weiss at dweiss@csu.fullerton.edu or Dr. Robertson at 657-278-3567, srobertson@fullerton.edu. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7640, or

e-mail irb@fullerton.edu. The researchers named above have no financial or other conflict of interest relating to results of this project.

I have carefully read this letter and consent and/or I have had the terms used in this letter and consent and their significance explained to me. By signing below, I state that I am at least 18 years of age, and I agree to participate in this project.

Participant's Name (please print): _____

Participant's Signature: _____

Researcher's Signature: _____

APPENDIX C-1

ORIGINAL HF ZONE TOOL FROM VNAA
BLUEPRINT FOR EXCELLENCE WEBSITE

CONGESTIVE HEART FAILURE ZONES for MANAGEMENT

Name: _____

Date: _____

<p align="center">Green Zone: All Clear</p> <p>Your Admission Weight: _____ Your Goal weight: _____</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No shortness of breath No swelling No weight gain No chest pain No decrease in your ability to maintain your activity level 	<p align="center">Green Zone Means:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Your symptoms are under control Continue taking your medications as ordered Continue daily weights Follow low salt diet Keep all your physician appointments
<p align="center">Yellow Zone: Caution</p> <p>If you have any of the following symptoms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased weight (2-3 lbs. in one day or 4-5 lbs. in the past 5 days) Increased cough Increased swelling of legs, feet and/or ankles Increased shortness of breath with activity Increase in the number of pillows needed Anything else that bothers you <p>Call your AGENCY NAME nurse EARLY in the day, or as soon as the symptoms occur.</p> <p>You are in the YELLOW ZONE.</p>	<p align="center">Yellow Zone Means:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Your symptoms indicate you need an adjustment of your medications <p align="center">AGENCY NAME PHONE NUMBER</p> <p align="center"></p>
<p align="center">Red Zone: Medical Alert</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unrelieved symptoms of shortness of breath, or shortness of breath at rest Unrelieved chest pain Wheezing or chest tightness at rest Need to sit in a chair to sleep Weight gain of more than 5 lbs. Confusion or mental status changes <p>** CALL YOUR PHYSICIAN IMMEDIATELY</p>	<p align="center">Red Zone Means:</p> <p>This indicates you need to be evaluated by a physician right away.</p> <p>Physician: _____</p> <p>Number: _____</p> <p align="right"></p>

APPENDIX C-2

EMAIL CORRESPONDENCE WITH LIZA GREENBERG TO OBTAIN PERMISSION TO USE VNAA ZONE TOOL

From: Daniel Weiss [mailto:Daniel.Weiss@sharp.com]
Sent: Monday, February 08, 2016 10:50 PM
To: Liza Greenberg
Subject: RE: VNAA Blueprint for Excellence

Hi Liza,

Thank you for your email message. I am a DNP student at Cal State Fullerton and a Palliative Care nurse at Sharp HospiceCare Transitions program in San Diego County. For my doctoral project, I am planning to implement a QI pilot project utilizing a Zones for Self-Management patient education tool with CHF patients, and I will be measuring patients' symptom burden, quality of life and CHF self-care index scores pre- and post-intervention.

Of the several CHF "zone tools" (or "stoplight tools") that I found online, the tool that I would most prefer to use for this project is your CHF zone tool that is included in VNAA's Blueprint for Excellence webpage. I called Heather Corbin last Friday to inquire about using your zone tool, with some modifications to fit our program's practice pattern, and she has referred me to you. With your permission, we will certainly give proper attribution to VNAA's Blueprint for Excellence as the source of this tool, noting that it has been adapted from your tool.

I would like to discuss this proposed project and use of your zone tool with you in greater detail by phone soon. Please call me at [619-871-3409](tel:619-871-3409) so that we can discuss this project and the process for obtaining your permission for using and adapting your zone tool.

Thanks again for your kind consideration,

Dan Weiss. RN. MS. CHPN

From: Liza Greenberg [L.Greenberg@vnaa.org]
Sent: Tuesday, February 09, 2016 9:11 AM
To: Daniel Weiss
Subject: RE: VNAA Blueprint for Excellence

Hi Daniel -

I looked up the Zone Tool on VNAA's Blueprint in the heart failure section, and couldn't find any copyright information on the document. All of our tools came from other organizations and are used with permission. We do not own the copyright but at some point before my time we got permission to post them and have others use them with attribution to the developer. Since no developer is listed on this tool, if you'd like to attribute the VNAA Blueprint for Excellence as the source of the version you used, that would be fine.

Also, FYI I googled some of the words from the document on our site and found that the exact words are used in multiple tools publicly available on the web. Example here: <http://mpqhf.com/QIO/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/Passporttohearthealth.pdf>

I don't know the rules of use for materials that are basically in the public domain, but you probably do.

Call or email me if you need more, but bottom line, you are welcome to adapt what's on our Blueprint. Good luck in your program. Liza

E. Liza Greenberg, RN, MPH
Interim Vice President, Quality and Performance Improvement Visiting Nurse Associations of America
2121 Crystal Drive, Suite 750, Arlington, VA 22202
Direct: [301-928-5909](tel:301-928-5909) | F: [571-527-1521](tel:571-527-1521)
Lgreenberg@vnaa.org | www.VNAA.org

APPENDIX D-1

SHARP TRANSITIONS ADAPTED HF ZONE TOOL -
INSIDE VIEW OF TRI-FOLD PAMPHLET

HEART FAILURE - ZONES FOR SELF MANAGEMENT

	Green Zone: All Clear	Yellow Zone: Caution	Red Zone: Medical Alert
HOW ARE YOU FEELING?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Your usual weight: _____ Trouble breathing during activity Little or no swelling in feet, ankles or legs. Little or no swelling in belly Little or no tiredness during normal activities 		
WHAT TO DO	<p>Your symptoms are under control</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Record weight every morning Continue medications as ordered Keep activity as tolerated Follow low salt diet as instructed by nurse/doctor Monitor symptoms daily and note any changes 	<p>Your symptoms are increasing or getting worse</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Call your Transitions nurse EARLY in the day or when symptoms increase 619-667-1900 You may need a change in your medications 	<p>Your symptoms are becoming severe or much worse</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Call your Transitions nurse immediately 619- 667-1900 or call your doctor You need to be evaluated by your nurse or doctor TODAY!

Adapted with permission from VNAA Blueprint for Excellence

HF ZONE TOOL - OUTSIDE VIEW OF TRI-FOLD PAMPHLET

<p>_____ Primary Doctor</p> <p>_____ Phone Number</p> <p><u>TRANSITIONS STAFF:</u></p> <p>_____ Nurse Case Manager:</p> <p>_____ Social Worker:</p> <p><u>NEVER BE AFRAID TO CALL IF YOU HAVE ANY QUESTIONS OR A CHANGE IN CONDITION.</u></p> <p>619-667-1900</p> <p>Between the hours of 5:00 p.m.—8:00 a.m. your call will be answered by the Sharp Grossmont Hospital Operator. Please identify yourself as a Sharp Hospice Care “Transitions Program” patient. The on-call nurse will return your call.</p>	<p>IMPROVING QUALITY OF LIFE</p> <p>When you have a chronic illness such as heart failure, you may find yourself feeling overwhelmed as your disease progresses. Transitions uses home-based palliative care to enhance your daily lifestyle through education, medication management and caregiver support.</p> <p>The Transitions program is a consultative service and is personalized to address your unique physical, emotional and spiritual needs. Your assigned nurse case manager, social worker and support staff will coordinate care with your physician.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> 619-667-1900 </p>	
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Adapted by Sharp Transitions Team with permission from VNAA Blueprint for Excellence

APPENDIX D-2

DAILY HF SELF-MONITORING CHART (COMPANION TO HF ZONE TOOL)

Heart Failure Zones for Self-management

Daily Self-checkup

Month: _____	Weight (Amount gained or lost in past day/week)	Swelling in Feet, Ankles, Legs (none, little, more than usual, severe)	Trouble Breathing at rest or with activity (none, little, more than usual, severe)	Tiredness (none, little, more than usual, severe)	Zone: (Green, Yellow, Red)
Date:					
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					
9					
10					
11					
12					
13					
14					
15					
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23					
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25					
26					
27					
28					
29					
30					
31					

Transitions Program
Advanced Illness Management

(619) 667-1900

APPENDIX E**CURRENT SHARP TRANSITIONS HF DECISION-SUPPORT TOOL****SHARP****TRANSITIONS – CHF**

**Know when to call your nurse
(619) 667-1900 or 1 (800) 681-9188**

- Weight gain 2-3 pounds in one day or 4 pounds in a week or less
- Problems breathing at night; using extra pillows to prop you up
- Change in your ability to sleep, especially waking up after falling asleep with shortness of breath
- Increased swelling in lower extremities
- Increased swelling, bloating or pain in abdomen (belly)
- Increased coughing, wheezing or shortness of breath
- Coughing white sputum or a dry hacking cough
- Increased fatigue
- Decreasing ability to be active, unable to do what you usually do
- New chest pains or chronic (old) chest pain which does not respond to nitroglycerin

Between the hours of 5:00 p.m. – 8:00 a.m. your call will be answered by the Sharp Grossmont Hospital operator. Please identify yourself as a Sharp HospiceCare "Transitions Program" patient. The Transitions on-call nurse will return your call.

From Sharp Transitions Program's Patient/Caregiver Education Materials

APPENDIX F-1

NEWEST VITAL SIGN (NVS) TOOL - NUTRITION LABEL

Nutrition Facts			
Serving Size		½ cup	
Servings per container		4	
<hr/>			
Amount per serving			
Calories	250	Fat Cal	120
			%DV
Total Fat	13g		20%
Sat Fat	9g		40%
Cholesterol	28mg		12%
Sodium	55mg		2%
Total Carbohydrate	30g		12%
Dietary Fiber	2g		
Sugars	23g		
Protein	4g		8%

*Percentage Daily Values (DV) are based on a 2,000 calorie diet. Your daily values may be higher or lower depending on your calorie needs.

Ingredients: Cream, Skim Milk, Liquid Sugar, Water, Egg Yolks, Brown Sugar, Milkfat, Peanut Oil, Sugar, Butter, Salt, Carrageenan, Vanilla Extract.

APPENDIX F-2

**NEWEST VITAL SIGN (NVS) TOOL -
SCORING SHEET WITH QUESTIONS & ANSWERS**

Score Sheet for the Newest Vital Sign

Questions and Answers

	ANSWER CORRECT?	
	yes	no
<p>READ TO SUBJECT: This information is on the back of a container of a pint of ice cream.</p>		
<p>1. If you eat the entire container, how many calories will you eat? <i>Answer: 1,000 is the only correct answer</i></p>		
<p>2. If you are allowed to eat 60 grams of carbohydrates as a snack, how much ice cream could you have? <i>Answer: Any of the following is correct: 1 cup (or any amount up to 1 cup), half the container. Note: If patient answers "two servings," ask "How much ice cream would that be if you were to measure it into a bowl?"</i></p>		
<p>3. Your doctor advises you to reduce the amount of saturated fat in your diet. You usually have 42 g of saturated fat each day, which includes one serving of ice cream. If you stop eating ice cream, how many grams of saturated fat would you be consuming each day? <i>Answer: 33 is the only correct answer</i></p>		
<p>4. If you usually eat 2,300 calories in a day, what percentage of your daily value of calories will you be eating if you eat one serving? <i>Answer: 10% is the only correct answer</i></p>		
<p>READ TO SUBJECT: Pretend that you are allergic to the following substances: penicillin, peanuts, latex gloves, and bee stings.</p>		
<p>5. Is it safe for you to eat this ice cream? <i>Answer: No</i></p>		
<p>6. (Ask only if the patient responds "no" to question 5): Why not? <i>Answer: Because it has peanut oil.</i></p>		
Number of correct answers:		

Interpretation
 Score of 0-1 suggests high likelihood (50% or more) of limited literacy.
 Score of 2-3 indicates the possibility of limited literacy.
 Score of 4-6 almost always indicates adequate literacy.

Working together for a healthier world®

February 2011

APPENDIX F-3

EMAIL CORRESPONDENCE WITH BARRY WEISS TO OBTAIN PERMISSION TO USE NVS TOOL

Daniel Weiss <danweiss0312@csu.fullerton.edu>

5/2/16 ☆

to bdweiss ▾

Dr. Weiss,

I am a DNP student at Cal State Fullerton, currently developing my doctoral project proposal. For this pilot project, I will be implementing use of a Heart Failure Zones for Self-Management decision support tool (adapted with permission from VNAA's Blueprint for Excellence) with a sample of patients with advanced HF. These patients are enrolled in the Sharp Transitions program, which provides home-based palliative care services, and where I work as a Clinical Nurse/Case Manager.

My two main outcomes of interest for this pilot project are HF Self-Care and HF-specific health status, which I plan to measure pre- and post-intervention. For measuring subjects' self-care, I will be using the Self-care of Heart Failure Index (SCHFI v6.2). In order to measure subjects' HF-related health status, I plan to use the shortened Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire (KCCQ-12).

I additionally plan to screen participants' health literacy using your Newest Vital Sign (NVS) tool, which I have located, along with instructions for administering and scoring the tool, on Pfizer's website. Although this tool and the accompanying toolkit online appear to be freely available in the public domain, I am nonetheless requesting your written permission to use the NVS tool (in English and Spanish) for this doctoral project. I am also planning to submit this project for eventual publication.

With your permission, I will provide proper attribution to you and your colleagues for use of this tool in my project proposal and final report. I will also properly cite your 2005 article "Quick Assessment of Literacy in Primary Care: The Newest Vital Sign" in Annals of Family Medicine.

I look forward to hearing from you soon.

Best regards,

Daniel J. Weiss, RN, MS, CHPN
CSU Southern California Consortium DNP Student

Weiss, Barry D - (bdweiss) <bdweiss@email.arizona.edu>

5/2/16 ☆

to me ▾

Daniel

You don't need any special permission to use the NVS for research or clinical purposes. I'm attaching some pdf copies of the NVS and the scores sheets. You can laminate them and use them in the study. Also attaching some FAQs.

The only thing for which you would need permission is if you plan to publish an image of the NVS in a journal. For that you would need permission from the Annals and Family Medicine and also from Pfizer, which holds the copyrights to the instrument; they have granted permission (for free) for such purposes but it may be easier just to describe the instrument in the text of an article.

- Barry

APPENDIX G

CHARLSON COMORBIDITY INDEX (CCI) - WEIGHTED INDEX CHART

Table 3. Weighted index of comorbidity

Assigned weights for diseases	Conditions
1	Myocardial infarct Congestive heart failure Peripheral vascular disease Cerebrovascular disease Dementia Chronic pulmonary disease Connective tissue disease Ulcer disease Mild liver disease Diabetes
2	Hemiplegia Moderate or severe renal disease Diabetes with end organ damage Any tumor Leukemia Lymphoma
3	Moderate or severe liver disease
6	Metastatic solid tumor AIDS

Assigned weights for each condition that a patient has. The total equals the score. Example: chronic pulmonary (1) and lymphoma (2) = total score (3).

APPENDIX H-1

SELF-CARE OF HEART FAILURE INDEX V.6.2

I

SELF-CARE OF HEART FAILURE INDEX

All answers are confidential.

Think about how you have been feeling in the last month or since we last spoke as you complete these items.

SECTION A:

Listed below are common instructions given to persons with heart failure. How routinely do you do the following?

	Never or rarely	Sometimes	Frequently	Always or daily
1. Weigh yourself?	1	2	3	4
2. Check your ankles for swelling?	1	2	3	4
3. Try to avoid getting sick (e.g., flu shot, avoid ill people)?	1	2	3	4
4. Do some physical activity?	1	2	3	4
5. Keep doctor or nurse appointments?	1	2	3	4
6. Eat a low salt diet?	1	2	3	4
7. Exercise for 30 minutes?	1	2	3	4
8. Forget to take one of your medicines?	1	2	3	4
9. Ask for low salt items when eating out or visiting others?	1	2	3	4
10. Use a system (pill box, reminders) to help you remember your medicines?	1	2	3	4

SECTION B:

Many patients have symptoms due to their heart failure. Trouble breathing and ankle swelling are common symptoms of heart failure.

In the past month, have you had trouble breathing or ankle swelling? Circle one.

- 0) No
- 1) Yes

11. If you had trouble breathing or ankle swelling in the past month...

(circle one number)

	Have not had these	I did not recognize it	Not Quickly	Somewhat Quickly	Quickly	Very Quickly
How quickly did you recognize it as a symptom of heart failure?	N/A	0	1	2	3	4

Listed below are remedies that people with heart failure use. If you have trouble breathing or ankle swelling, how likely are you to try one of these remedies?

(circle one number for each remedy)

	Not Likely	Somewhat Likely	Likely	Very Likely
12. Reduce the salt in your diet	1	2	3	4
13. Reduce your fluid intake	1	2	3	4
14. Take an extra water pill	1	2	3	4
15. Call your doctor or nurse for guidance	1	2	3	4

16. Think of a remedy you tried the last time you had trouble breathing or ankle swelling.

(circle one number)

	I did not try anything	Not Sure	Somewhat Sure	Sure	Very Sure
How sure were you that the remedy helped or did not help?	0	1	2	3	4

SECTION C:

In general, how confident are you that you can:

	Not Confident	Somewhat Confident	Very Confident	Extremely Confident
17. <u>Keep yourself free of heart failure symptoms?</u>	1	2	3	4
18. <u>Follow the treatment advice you have been given?</u>	1	2	3	4
19. <u>Evaluate the importance of your symptoms?</u>	1	2	3	4
20. <u>Recognize changes in your health if they occur?</u>	1	2	3	4
21. <u>Do something that will relieve your symptoms?</u>	1	2	3	4
22. <u>Evaluate how well a remedy works?</u>	1	2	3	4

From Riegel (2015) Self-Care of Heart Failure Index Website
 Retrieved from: http://www.self-careofheartfailureindex.com/?page_id=6

APPENDIX H-2

CAREGIVER CONTRIBUTION TO SELF-CARE OF HEART FAILURE INDEX

CAREGIVER CONTRIBUTION TO SELF-CARE OF HEART FAILURE INDEX

All answers are confidential.

We kindly ask you to think about the care you have given to the person with Heart Failure in the past month. There are no right or wrong answers.

How often do you recommend to the person you care for the following things?
(Or, how often do you do these activities because the person you care for is not able to do them).

SECTION A:

	Never or rarely	Sometimes	Frequently	Always or daily
1. To check the weight ?	1	2	3	4
2. To check the ankles for swelling?	1	2	3	4
3. To try to avoid getting sick (e.g., flu shot, avoid ill people)?	1	2	3	4
4. To do some physical activity?	1	2	3	4
5. To keep doctor or nurse appointments?	1	2	3	4
6. To eat a low salt diet?	1	2	3	4
7. To exercise for 30 minutes?	1	2	3	4
8. To not forget to take medicines?	1	2	3	4
9. To ask for low salt items when eating out or visiting others?	1	2	3	4
10. To use a system (pill box, reminders) to help you remember your medicines?	1	2	3	4

SECTION B:

Many patients have symptoms due to their heart failure. Trouble breathing and ankle swelling are common symptoms of heart failure.

In the past month, did the person you care for have trouble breathing or ankle swelling? Circle one.

- 0) No
1) Yes

11. If the person you care for had trouble breathing or ankle swelling in the past month...

(circle one number)

	Has not had these	I did not recognize it	Not Quickly	Somewhat Quickly	Quickly	Very Quickly
How quickly did you recognize it as a symptom of heart failure?	N/A	0	1	2	3	4

If the person you care for has trouble breathing or ankle swelling, how likely are you to recommend (or do) one of these remedies?

(circle one number for each remedy)

	Not Likely	Somewhat Likely	Likely	Very Likely
12. To reduce the salt in the diet	1	2	3	4
13. To reduce fluid intake	1	2	3	4
14. To take an extra water pill	1	2	3	4
15. To call the doctor or nurse for guidance	1	2	3	4

16. Think of a remedy you tried the last time the person you care for had trouble breathing or ankle swelling,

(circle one number)

	I did not try anything	Not Sure	Somewhat Sure	Sure	Very Sure
How sure were you that the remedy helped or did not help?	0	1	2	3	4

SECTION C:

In reference to the person you care for, in general, how confident are you that you can:

	Not Confident	Somewhat Confident	Very Confident	Extremely Confident
17. Keep him/her <u>free of heart failure symptoms?</u>	1	2	3	4
18. <u>Follow the given treatment advice?</u>	1	2	3	4
19. <u>Evaluate the importance of symptoms?</u>	1	2	3	4
20. <u>Recognize changes in him/her health when they occur?</u>	1	2	3	4
21. <u>Do something that will relieve him/her symptoms?</u>	1	2	3	4
22. <u>Evaluate</u> how well a remedy works?	1	2	3	4

Retrieved from Self-Care of Heart Failure Index website:
http://www.self-careofheartfailureindex.com/?page_id=38

APPENDIX H-3

EMAIL CORRESPONDENCE WITH BARBARA RIEGEL
TO OBTAIN PERMISSION TO USE SCHFI V.6.2

Daniel Weiss <danweiss0312@csu.fullerton.edu>

2/22/16 ☆

to briegel ▾

Hi Dr. Riegel,

I am a doctoral student in CSU Southern California Consortium's DNP program. I also work as a Clinical Nurse at Sharp HospiceCare's Transitions Program, which provides home-based palliative care for patients with advanced chronic illness, including CHF.

For my scholarly doctoral project, I will be implementing a pilot project using a CHF Zones for Self-Management tool for patient education and will be doing pre- and post-intervention measurements of Quality of Life and Self Care. I am requesting your permission to utilize your Self Care of Heart Failure Index (SCHFI V 6.2), with proper attribution, for this pilot project and doctoral project.

I look forward to your reply and further correspondence with you regarding this project.

Best regards,
Daniel J. Weiss, RN, MS, CHPN
CSU Southern California Consortium DNP Student

Riegel, Barbara <briegel@nursing.upenn.edu>

2/22/16 ☆

to me ▾

Hello Daniel, you are welcome to use the SCHFI. It's freely available on the website and you don't really need permission to use it. Good luck with your project.

Barbara Riegel, PhD, RN, FAHA, FAAN
Professor and Edith Clemmer Steinbright Chair of Gerontology
Director, Biobehavioral Interest Group (BIG)
Senior Fellow, Leonard Davis Institute
University of Pennsylvania, School of Nursing

APPENDIX I-1

KANSAS CITY CARDIOMYOPATHY QUESTIONNAIRE SHORT FORM
(KCCQ-12)*Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire (KCCQ-12)*

The following questions refer to your **heart failure** and how it may affect your life. Please read and complete the following questions. There are no right or wrong answers. Please mark the answer that best applies to you.

1. **Heart failure** affects different people in different ways. Some feel shortness of breath while others feel fatigue. Please indicate how much you are limited by **heart failure** (shortness of breath or fatigue) in your ability to do the following activities over the past 2 weeks.

Activity	Extremely Limited	Quite a bit Limited	Moderately Limited	Slightly Limited	Not at all Limited	Limited for other reasons or did not do the activity
a. Showering/bathing	<input type="radio"/>					
b. Walking 1 block on level ground	<input type="radio"/>					
c. Hurrying or jogging (as if to catch a bus)	<input type="radio"/>					
	1	2	3	4	5	6

2. Over the past 2 weeks, how many times did you have **swelling** in your feet, ankles or legs when you woke up in the morning?

Every morning	3 or more times per week but not every day	1-2 times per week	Less than once a week	Never over the past 2 weeks
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
1	2	3	4	5

3. Over the past 2 weeks, on average, how many times has **fatigue** limited your ability to do what you wanted?

All of the time	Several times per day	At least once a day	3 or more times per week but not every day	1-2 times per week	Less than once a week	Never over the past 2 weeks
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

4. Over the past 2 weeks, on average, how many times has **shortness of breath** limited your ability to do what you wanted?

All of the time	Several times per day	At least once a day	3 or more times per week but not every day	1-2 times per week	Less than once a week	Never over the past 2 weeks
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

5. Over the past 2 weeks, on average, how many times have you been forced to sleep sitting up in a chair or with at least 3 pillows to prop you up because of **shortness of breath**?

Every night	3 or more times per week but not every day	1-2 times per week	Less than once a week	Never over the past 2 weeks
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
1	2	3	4	5

6. Over the past 2 weeks, how much has your **heart failure** limited your enjoyment of life?

It has extremely limited my enjoyment of life	It has limited my enjoyment of life quite a bit	It has moderately limited my enjoyment of life	It has slightly limited my enjoyment of life	It has not limited my enjoyment of life at all
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
1	2	3	4	5

7. If you had to spend the rest of your life with your **heart failure** the way it is right now, how would you feel about this?

Not at all satisfied	Mostly dissatisfied	Somewhat satisfied	Mostly satisfied	Completely satisfied
<input type="radio"/>				
1	2	3	4	5

8. How much does your **heart failure** affect your lifestyle? Please indicate how your **heart failure** may have limited your participation in the following activities over the past 2 weeks.

Activity	Severely Limited	Limited quite a bit	Moderately limited	Slightly limited	Did not limit at all	Does not apply or did not do for other reasons
a. Hobbies, recreational activities	<input type="radio"/>					
b. Working or doing household chores	<input type="radio"/>					
c. Visiting family or friends out of your home	<input type="radio"/>					
	1	2	3	4	5	6

From Spertus & Jones (2015), Appendix 2

APPENDIX I-2

EMAIL CORRESPONDENCE WITH JOHN SPERTUS
TO OBTAIN PERMISSION TO USE KCCQ-12

Daniel Weiss <danweiss0312@csu.fullerton.edu>

4/29/16 ☆

to spertusj ▾

Dr. Spertus,

I am a DNP student at Cal State Fullerton. currently developing my doctoral project proposal. For this pilot project, I will be implementing use of a Heart Failure Zones for Self-Management decision support tool (adapted with permission from VNAA's Blueprint for Excellence) with a sample of patients with advanced HF. These patients are enrolled in the Sharp Transitions program, which provides home-based palliative care services, and where I work as a Clinical Nurse/Case Manager.

My two main outcomes of interest are HF Self-Care and HF-specific Quality of Life, which I plan to measure pre- and post-intervention. For measuring subjects' self-care, I have obtained permission from Dr. Barbara Riegel at Penn to use her Self-Care of Heart Failure Index (SCHDI v6.2).

In order to measure subjects' quality of life, I am requesting your permission to use the shortened Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire (KCCQ-12) for this doctoral project. I have chosen this tool for its HF specificity, well-documented reliability, validity, and relative ease of administration.

With your permission, I will of course provide proper attribution to you and your colleagues for use of this tool in my project proposal and final report. I will also properly cite your 2015 article "Development and validation of a short version of the Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire" in Circulation Cardiovascular Quality Outcomes. Please let me know if there is a user guide for administration and scoring of the KCCQ-12 and how to obtain this user guide.

I look forward to hearing from you soon.

Best regards,

Daniel J. Weiss, RN, MS, CHPN
CSU Southern California Consortium DNP Student

Spertus, John <spertusj@umkc.edu>

5/1/16 ☆

to Stan, me ▾

Thank you so much for reaching out, Dan. I am sorry for the delay in responding. Please go to www.cvoutcomes.org to request a license and whatever translations (e.g. Spanish) you need. We have a very inexpensive price for student projects like this, but if that is a problem, then just let us know. Also, there are scoring instructions and for student projects we strongly encourage you to program those, rather than purchasing a scoring program from us so that you can get a more visceral understanding of the instrument. Good luck with your project.

John

APPENDIX I-3

LICENSE FROM CV OUTCOMES FOR USE OF KCCQ-12

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Pilot study of a Heart Failure Zones for Self-management tool

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Project Information

Name	Pilot study of a Heart Failure Zones for Self-management tool
Type	Pilot study for Doctoral Project (DNP)
Dates	Start: 08/01/2016 End: 08/01/2017 Duration: 365 days
Enrollment	Sites: 1 Average Subjects per Site: 30 Total Subjects: 30
Schedule of Use	Administer to each subject 3 times at these events: 1. Upon enrollment in pilot study; 2. 25-35 days after enrollment; 3. 55-65 days after enrollment Total Uses: 90
Contact	Dan Weiss
Sponsor Name	California State University - Fullerton
Sponsor Type	University where I am completing DNP degree
Project Motivation	Not for sponsor profit
Contact Role in Project	Principal investigator (DNP student)

Organization [Edit](#)

Name	California State University - Fullerton
Contact Name	Dan Weiss
Contact Title	School of Nursing
Contact Email	danweiss0312@csu.fullerton.edu
Address 1	800 N. State College Blvd
Address 2	n/a
City	Fullerton
State	California
Province	n/a
Postal Code	92831
Additional Info	Pilot study will be implemented at Sharp Transitions Program in San Diego County, where Dan Weiss works as a Clinical Nurse/Case Mgr. This program provides home-based palliative care to patients with advanced chronic illnesses, including Heart Failure.

Licensed Items

KCCQ-12 - English (US) Download	This version of the KCCQ-12 has been validated among English-speaking residents of the US. This zip file includes two PDF files: the KCCQ-12 itself and scoring instructions.
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APPENDIX J-1

POST-COMPLETION SURVEY FOR PARTICIPANTS -
CONTROL GROUPParticipant Survey

Thank you very much for participating in our evidence-based practice pilot project.

We value your opinions and suggestions.

For each question below, please check the response that best matches your opinion.

1. How hard or easy to understand was the Heart Failure "Know When to Call Your Nurse" tool?

Very Hard	Somewhat Hard	Neither hard nor easy	Somewhat Easy	Very Easy
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

2. How helpful or unhelpful was the Heart Failure "Know When to Call Your Nurse" tool for recognizing signs & symptoms of worsening heart failure to report to the nurse?

Very unhelpful	Somewhat unhelpful	Neither helpful nor unhelpful	Somewhat helpful	Very helpful
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3. How hard or easy was the Newest Vital Sign test to understand and complete?

Very Hard	Somewhat Hard	Neither hard nor easy	Somewhat Easy	Very Easy
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. How hard or easy was the Self-Care of Heart Failure Index tool to understand and complete?

Very Hard	Somewhat Hard	Neither hard nor easy	Somewhat Easy	Very Easy
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

5. How hard or easy was the Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire (KCCQ-12) tool to understand and complete?

Very Hard	Somewhat Hard	Neither hard nor easy	Somewhat Easy	Very Easy
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(Continue on other side)

Participant Survey (continued)

6. In a few words, please describe anything you liked about participating in this research study:

7. In a few words, please describe anything you disliked about participating in this study:

8. Please share your suggestions for anything we could do to improve this research study:

APPENDIX J-2

POST-COMPLETION SURVEY FOR PARTICIPANTS -
INTERVENTION GROUPParticipant Survey

Thank you for participating in our evidence-based practice pilot project.

We value your opinions and suggestions.

For each question below, please check the response that best matches your opinion.

1. How hard or easy to understand was the Heart Failure "Know When to Call Your Nurse" tool?

Very Hard	Somewhat Hard	Neither hard nor easy	Somewhat Easy	Very Easy
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

2. How helpful or unhelpful was the Heart Failure "Know When to Call Your Nurse" tool for recognizing signs & symptoms of worsening heart failure to report to the nurse?

Very unhelpful	Somewhat unhelpful	Neither helpful nor unhelpful	Somewhat helpful	Very helpful
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3. How hard or easy to understand was the Heart Failure Zones for Self-Management tool?

Very Hard	Somewhat Hard	Neither hard nor easy	Somewhat Easy	Very Easy
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

4. How helpful or unhelpful was the Heart Failure Zones for Self-Management tool for recognizing signs & symptoms of worsening heart failure to report to the nurse?

Very unhelpful	Somewhat unhelpful	Neither helpful nor unhelpful	Somewhat helpful	Very helpful
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

5. How hard or easy was the Newest Vital Sign tool to understand and complete?

Very Hard	Somewhat Hard	Neither hard nor easy	Somewhat Easy	Very Easy
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

6. How hard or easy was the Self-Care of Heart Failure Index tool to understand and complete?

Very Hard	Somewhat Hard	Neither hard nor easy	Somewhat Easy	Very Easy
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(Continue on other side)

Participant Survey (continued)

7. How hard or easy was the Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire (KCCQ-12) tool to understand and complete?

Very Hard Somewhat Hard Neither hard nor easy Somewhat Easy Very Easy

8. In a few words, please describe anything you liked about participating in this research study:

9. In a few words, please describe anything you disliked about participating in this study:

10. Please share your suggestions for anything we could do to improve this research study:

APPENDIX J-3

POST-COMPLETION SURVEY FOR NURSES

Nurse Survey

For each question below, please check the response that best matches your opinion.

1. How hard or easy was the Heart Failure "Know When to Call Your Nurse" tool for the study participants to understand?

Very Hard <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat Hard <input type="radio"/>	Neither hard nor easy <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat Easy <input type="radio"/>	Very Easy <input type="radio"/>
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2. How helpful or unhelpful was the Heart Failure "Know When to Call Your Nurse" tool for participants to recognize signs & symptoms of worsening heart failure to report to the nurse?

Very unhelpful <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat unhelpful <input type="radio"/>	Neither helpful nor unhelpful <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat helpful <input type="radio"/>	Very helpful <input type="radio"/>
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3. How hard or easy was the Heart Failure Zones for Self-Management tool for participants to understand?

Very Hard <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat Hard <input type="radio"/>	Neither hard nor easy <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat Easy <input type="radio"/>	Very Easy <input type="radio"/>
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4. How helpful or unhelpful was the Heart Failure Zones for Self-Management tool for participants to recognize signs & symptoms of worsening heart failure to report to the nurse?

Very unhelpful <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat unhelpful <input type="radio"/>	Neither helpful nor unhelpful <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat helpful <input type="radio"/>	Very helpful <input type="radio"/>
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5. How hard or easy was the Newest Vital Sign tool for participants to understand and complete?

Very Hard <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat Hard <input type="radio"/>	Neither hard nor easy <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat Easy <input type="radio"/>	Very Easy <input type="radio"/>
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6. How hard or easy was the Self-Care of Heart Failure Index tool for participants to understand and complete?

Very Hard <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat Hard <input type="radio"/>	Neither hard nor easy <input type="radio"/>	Somewhat Easy <input type="radio"/>	Very Easy <input type="radio"/>
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(Continue on other side)

Nurse Survey (cont'd.)

7. How hard or easy was the Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire (KCCQ-12) for participants to understand and complete?

Very	Somewhat	Neither hard	Somewhat	Very
Hard	Hard	nor easy	Easy	Easy
<input type="radio"/>				

8. In a few words, please describe anything you liked about helping conduct this research study:

9. In a few words, please describe anything you disliked about helping conduct this study:

10. Please share your suggestions for anything we could do to improve this research study:

APPENDIX K

TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Table A1. *Systematic & Integrative Reviews of HF Self-Care Interventions*

Purpose (Authors, year)	Design; Key Outcomes	Review time frame; # & sources of studies; search terms	Measurements; Operational Definitions of Variables	Results/Findings; Conclusions/Recommendations
To assess the effectiveness of self-management interventions in patients with HF and whether subgroups of patients respond differently (Jonkman et al., 2016)	Individual pt. data (IPD) meta-analysis IV's: - HF Self-mgmt., interventions DV's: HF-related outcomes: - time to combined end point of HF-related hospitalization or all-cause death - time to first HF-related hospitalization - total days of HF-related hospital stay at 12 months - HF-QoL at 12 months General outcomes: - generic QoL at 12 months - time to all-cause death - time to first all-cause hospitalization & total days of all-cause hospital stay at 12 months - Pt. satisfaction	1985 - 2013 Meta-analysis of 20 RCT's (N=5624) Searched PubMed, EMBASE, CENTRAL, PsycINFO, CINAHL, as well as reference lists of systematic reviews Data analyzed w/ mixed-effects models & Cox proportional-hazard models, including interaction terms	- HFQoL, measured w/ HFSS, KCCQ, MHDHRQLI , MLWHFQ - Generic QoL, measured w/ SFHS-12 or SFHS-36	Self-mgmt. interventions: - reduced risk of time to combined end point of HF-related hospitalization or all-cause death - reduced risk of time to HF-related hospitalization - improved 12-month HF-related quality of life - No effects found for: - total days in hospital as a result of HF readmissions - any of the general outcomes Subgroup analyses revealed: - protective effect of self-mgmt. on # of HF-related hospital days in pts. <65 years of age. - pts. w/o depression did not show an effect of self-management on survival. - in pts. with moderate/severe depression, self-mgmt. reduced survival.

<p>To determine effectiveness of structured telephone support (STS) or noninvasive home telemonitoring (NIHT) in reducing all-cause mortality, all-cause & HF-related hospitalizations and improving HRQoL, HF knowledge, self-care.</p> <p>(Inglis et al., 2015)</p>	<p>Systematic Review</p> <p>IV's: - STS - HITP</p> <p>DV's: Primary outcomes: - All-cause mortality - All-cause hospitalizations - HF-related hospitalizations</p> <p>Secondary outcomes: - HRQoL - HF knowledge - HF self-care - Pt. satisfaction</p>	<p>2008 to 2015, Cochrane Review of 41 RCT's (updated 2 earlier Cochrane reviews from 1966-2006 & 2006-2008)</p> <p>Searched 8 databases, 3 online resources, 7 organizations' conference proceedings, plus hand-searched bibliographies 50+ search terms, including: <i>heart failure, telemedicine, telemonitor, case mgmt., disease mgmt.</i></p>	<p>- All-cause mortality - All-cause hospitalizations - HF-related hospitalizations</p> <p>all analyzed using a fixed-effect model</p> <p>Data presented as RR's with 95% CI's</p>	<p>- NIHT reduced all-cause mortality (mod. -quality evidence) & HF-related hospitalizations (mod. -quality evidence). - STS reduced all-cause mortality (mod. -quality evidence) & HF-related hospitalizations (mod. -quality evidence). - Neither STS nor NIHT reduced all-cause hospitalizations (very low-quality evidence). - 7 of 9 studies reported signif. improvements in HF knowledge & HF self-care behaviors.</p>
<p>To assess efficacy & comparative effectiveness of transitional care interventions (TCI's) in reducing readmission rates & mortality for adults hospitalized w/HF (Feltner et al., 2014)</p>	<p>Systematic review & meta-analysis</p> <p>IV's: TCI's: - Home-visiting pgms. - STS -Telemonitoring - Outpatient clinic-based - Primarily educational (before or at discharge)</p> <p>DV's: - # of readmissions - # of deaths</p>	<p>1990 - 2013 Review of 47 RCT's</p> <p>Databases searched: MEDLINE, Cochrane Database, CINAHL, WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform, ClinicalTrials.gov</p>	<p>- Home-visiting pgms.: home visits by nurses, pharmacists or multi-disciplinary teams. - STS: series of phone calls for monitoring, education or self-care mgmt. - Telemonitoring: remote monitoring of physiological data (Wt., BP, ECG, etc.) - Outpt. clinic-based: services provided in one of several types of clinics: primary care, nurse-led HF or multidisciplinary HF (MDS-HF) - Primarily educational: Pt. education & self-care training provided before or at discharge</p>	<p>Over 3-6 months, home visiting pgms. & MDS-HF clinic interventions reduced all-cause mortality (high SOE). - Home-visiting pgms. reduced HF-specific readmission (mod. SOE) - STS reduced HF-specific readmission (high SOE), but not all-cause readmissions (mod. SOE). - Home-visiting pgms., STS & MDS-HF clinic reduced mortality.</p>

<p>To examine efficacy of interventions used to improve HF self-care (self-maintenance & self-mgmt. behaviors) and pt.-related factors (HF knowledge, self-care efficacy/confidence, beliefs re: HF self-care)</p> <p>(Barnason, Zimmerman, & Young, 2012)</p>	<p>Integrative review</p> <p>IV's: - Interventions to improve HF self-care</p> <p>DV's: - Self-care maintenance & mgmt. behaviors - HF knowledge - HF self-care knowledge</p> <p>Situation-specific theory of HF self-care was conceptual model for this review.</p>	<p>2000 - 2010</p> <p>Review of 19 studies (all with IG & CG)</p> <p>Databases searched: Medline, CINAHL, Cochrane Database, PsychInfo, plus hand search of references in studies & reviews</p> <p>Search terms: <i>heart failure OR congestive heart failure AND self-care OR self-mgmt. OR self-monitoring OR self-regulation OR self-care skills AND intervention OR clinical trial OR pilot study OR outcomes OR RCT</i></p>	<p>Interventions included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One-time education or counseling session (4/19) - Initial education or counseling session w/ 1-2 follow-up sessions (5/19) - Daily telehealth interactions (1/19) - Initial intervention followed by periodic counseling/mentoring over 3-4 months (6/19) - Telephone follow-up sessions over 6 months (1/19) <p>Self-care measurements of single or multiple self-care behaviors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tools developed or adapted by researcher - HF self-care specific tools (SCHFI, etc.) - self-reported behaviors - objective measures of med adherence using Med e-Monitor, pharmacy refill records <p>Patient-related factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge of HF or HF self-care - Self-efficacy - Barriers and facilitators to HF self-care 	<p>- Neither telemonitoring nor primary education interventions reduced mortality or readmission.</p> <p>Efficacy for self-care:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Among the 17 studies measuring HF self-care, 13 had signif. improved self-care maintenance (usually single self-reported behaviors) & self-care mgmt. (using SCHFI) - All but 3 studies had higher use by IG of self-care behaviors (wt. monitoring, taking diuretics as prescribed, following low-sodium diet, smoking cessation) <p>Efficacy for pt.-related factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Most IG's showed higher HF knowledge & self-care knowledge, increased self-efficacy, improved QOL and perceptions of benefits of & barriers to HF self-care.
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Table A2. *Individual Studies of HF Self-care Interventions*

Purpose; (Authors, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements; Operational Definitions of Variables	Results/Findings; Conclusions/Recommendations
Evaluate effects of home-based HF education support intervention by APRN's to improve health status & self-care outcomes (Clark, 2015)	Prospective RCT 9-month study period IV: Home-based education & skill-building pgm. & phone/email support Primary outcomes: - functional status - emotional state; depressive sx - metamemory - knowledge/ retention - self-care ability Secondary: perceptions of intervention	N=50 (25 in IG; 25 in CG) Community-dwelling HF pts. University of Texas at Austin; Austin, TX	IV: 8 home visits by APRN's teaching 8 HF education modules & memory enhancement methods over 3 mos., then phone-email support for 3 mos., then no contact for 3 mos. DV- Primary Outcomes Health Status outcomes: - Functional status (KCCQ total score) - Self-efficacy (KCCQ subscale) - QoL (KCCQ subscale) - Emotional state (GDS) - Metamemory (MAQ Capacity, Change, External Strategies sub-scales) Self-Care outcomes: - Knowledge/Retention (HFKT) - Self-care (SCHFI) All measured at baseline, 3, 6 & 9 months	Primary outcomes: - IG signif. higher functional status at 3 mos. & at 6 mos. - IG signif. higher self-efficacy scores at 3, 6, 9 mos. - IG signif. higher QoL at 3 & 9 mos. - IG & CG both improved GDS - IG signif. higher metamemory capacity & change scores at 3, 6, 9 mos., while CG scores decreased over time - No signif. time-by-group effect in external strategies - IG signif. higher HF knowledge scores at 3, 6, 9 mos. - Self-care maintenance, confidence signif. higher over time for both IG & CG; IG improved more than CG. - Self-care management signif. higher for IG than CG at 6 mos.
To evaluate efficacy of a community-based skill building intervention on HF self-care, knowledge & HRQoL outcomes (Dickson, 2014)	Staggered RCT design pilot study w/ IG & wait-list CG (which was offered the intervention after 3 months) IV: Group-based HF self-care skill-building pgm. delivered by	N=75 (38 in IG, 37 in CG) at start of study; 56 (29 in IG, 27 in CG) at 3 months - HF pts. age 55+ living in community setting where they could provide self-care (not in LTC)	IV: Twice-weekly 60-minute group sessions for 4 weeks. Content: 4 areas of HF self-care skills (medication adherence; low-salt diet; sx monitoring; sx mgmt.) Intervention delivered by lay health educators w/ bachelors degrees & health education credentials. DV- Primary Outcomes: - Self-care (SCHFI maintenance &	Primary outcomes: - Self-care maintenance: improved in IG compared to CG. Significant interaction between group & time (mod. effect size). - Self-care mgmt. signif. improved in IG but not in CG. Signif. interaction between group & time (large effect size)

	<p>trained health educators + UC. UC: Standard HF pt. education by providers. DV's: - HF Self-Care - HF knowledge - HRQoL</p>	<p>- Intervention provided at 3 urban senior centers New York, NY & Philadelphia, PA</p>	<p>management subscales) - Knowledge (DHFKS) - HRQL (KCCQ clinical summary scale & overall score) All measured at baseline, 1 & 3 months</p>	<p>- HF knowledge: Signif. improvement in IG. (large interaction effect size) - HRQoL: No signif. difference between IG & CG. Both improved.</p>
<p>To evaluate efficacy of HF sx training pgm. on pts.' ability to recognize & respond to changes in HF sx and on event-free survival (Jurgens, 2013)</p>	<p>RCT pilot study (3-month study period) IV: HF SMART intervention (Somatic awareness & cognitive awareness training) + UC UC: Wt. scale provided w/ instructions re: daily wt. monitoring; HF self-care booklet. DV's: Primary outcome: - 90-day event-free survival Secondary outcomes: -HF sx awareness (HFSPS) - HF Self-Care (SCHFI)</p>	<p><i>N</i>=99 (48 in IG, 51 in CG) assessed after 3 months HF pts. (mean age 67.7) living in community Intervention + UC provided in hospital prior to discharge to home w/ IG receiving 1 f/u home visit by PI 7-10 days later Long Island, NY</p>	<p>IV - HF SMART intervention - Somatic awareness training: - Sx burden (0-10 scale) at rest noted on sx graph - Sx (dyspnea & fatigue) documented on sx graph after 6-minute walk test (done by 23 IG pts. who were medically stable, able & willing to do walk test). Cognitive awareness training: Pts. instructed re: meaning of sx, use of sx graph, appropriate response to sx (e.g. call provider, take extra diuretic) - Home visit after 7-10 days to review training DV's- Primary Outcome: - Event-free survival (measured at 1 & 3 months after baseline): composite end-point time to first event of HF hospitalization, ED admission for HF or HF-related cause, or death. Secondary Outcomes measured at baseline & 3 mos.: - HF Sx awareness (HFSPS) - HF Self-care (SCHFI maintenance & mgmt. subscales)</p>	<p>Primary outcome: - Event-free survival: No difference in survival time between IG & CG - IG had signif. improved self-care maintenance, mgmt. & confidence at 90-day follow-up. - IG had signif. improved self-care maintenance & mgmt. at 90-day follow-up - No signif. difference between groups. - Post-hoc power analysis determined that sample of 228 participants would be needed to detect signif. differences between groups in self-care scores. - No results reported re: HFSPS scores at baseline, at follow-up, or between IG & CG. Recommendations: - Multiple home visits (particularly in first 30 days post-discharge) are needed to help support intervention adherence.</p>

Table A3. *Studies of HF Self-Care Interventions Using Green-Yellow-Red Zone Tools*

Purpose; (Authors, year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results/Findings; Conclusions/Recommendations
Evaluate efficacy of a low-literacy HF self-mgmt. education pgm. in reducing hospitalizations and improving HFQoL (DeWalt et al., 2006)	RCT design IV: HF self-mgmt. education intervention DV--Primary outcomes: - Rate of death or all-cause readmissions after 12 months - HFQoL	<i>N</i> =127 HF pts. (62 in IG; 65 in CG) enrolled; 111 pts. (52 in IG; 59 in CG) completed 12-month follow-up University of North Carolina General Internal Medicine clinic Chapel Hill, NC	IV: HF self-mgmt. education intervention: - 1-hr. education session w/ pharmacist or health educator; pts. taught to recognize signs of HF exacerbation, check wt. daily, & self-adjust diuretic dose. - Low-literacy HF education booklet had green-yellow-red zone chart to record daily wt., LE swelling, diuretic dose taken - Digital scale provided to pts. - Follow-up phone calls (on days 3,7, 14, 21, 28, 56) and monthly during months 3-6, designed to reinforce HF education and provide motivation to pt. DV: Outcomes assessed at 6 & 12 months via in-person interviews & medical record review.	Results - Primary outcomes: - 42% of IG pts. vs. 61% of CG pts. had at least 1 hospitalization or died after 12 months. - 34% of IG pts. vis. 39% of CG pts. had 1+ cardiac admission. - No signif. difference between CG & IG in HFQoL. Other outcomes: - IG pts improved signif. more than CG pts. in HF knowledge, HF self-efficacy, daily wt. monitoring. Conclusions/Recommendations: - HF self-mgmt. intervention reduced hospitalization & death.
Compare effects of single-session vs. multisession low-literacy HF self-care intervention on incidence of all-cause hospitalization or death. (DeWalt et al., 2012)	RCT design IV - Single session HF self-care education vs. multiple HF self-care education sessions DV's--Primary outcome: - Rates of all-cause hospitalization or death Secondary outcomes: - Rates of HF-related hospitalization - Rates of ED visits	<i>N</i> =605 HF pts. (302 single-session; 303 multisession) University of North Carolina General Internal Medicine clinic Chapel Hill, NC	IV's--Single-session: Initial 40-minute training (per health educator) re: daily self-assessment, salt avoidance, med adherence, exercise, action plan in case of exacerbation, plus digital scale & HF self-care manual w/ green-yellow-red zone tool. Multisession: Same initial training session plus additional sessions w/ more intensive education & self-care training. DV's--Primary outcomes: In-person interviews at 6 & 12 months to determine if & where any hospitalization had occurred, followed by chart reviews re: ED visits/hospitalizations.	Primary outcomes: No differences between single-session & multisession groups for rates of all-cause hospitalization or death. Secondary outcomes: - HF-related hospitalization rate: lower in multisession vs. single-session; among lower-literacy pts. lower in multisession vs single-session group; among higher-literacy pts., lower in single-session vs. multisession group. - ED visit rate: no difference between multisession & single-

	- Subgroup analyses by literacy level - HFQoL		- Deaths confirmed via national death index using several databases (Social Security, etc.) Secondary outcomes: Reviewer(s) determined if hospitalization was HF-related. - Literacy (S-TOFHLA) - HFQoL (HFSS) at baseline, 1, 6, & 12 mos.	session groups; no difference by literacy. - HFQoL: Greater improvement in multisession group from baseline to 1 mo. & 6 mos.; no signif. difference 12 mos.
To evaluate the effect of a quality improvement (QI) initiative on 30-day readmissions of HF pts. (Simpson, 2014)	Pre- and post-implementation analysis IV: QI initiative DV: 30-day HF readmissions	<i>N</i> =57 pts. w/ high risk of readmission discharged from hospital to home Palm Beach Gardens Medical Ctr. Palm Beach Gardens, FL	IV: QI initiative - Risk stratification of HF admissions for likelihood of 30-day readmission - Intensive education (including green-yellow-red "zone map") for pts. at high risk for readmission - Post-discharge phone call to high-risk pts. DV: 30-day readmissions (% of high-risk pts. discharged to home who were readmitted within first 5 months of 2013, compared w/ % readmitted during same period in 2011.	Results: - 30-day readmission rate during first 5 months of 2013 was 18.95%, compared w/ 21.95% during same period in 2012 (an 8.5% decrease) Conclusions/Recommendations: - Emphasizing HF education in inpt. setting helps pts. manage HF post-discharge & reduces readmissions. Zone map is focus of HF inpt. education.
Evaluate feasibility of 2 pt. self-monitoring instruments re: HF Sx recognition & reporting (Wakefield, Groves, Drwal, Scherubel, & Kaboli, 2016)	Mixed-methods feasibility study; Pretest-posttest longitudinal design (3-month study period) IV: 2 paper-based graphs to monitor wt. & dyspnea DV's: Primary: - HF sx recognition - HF self-care - Reporting sx to providers	<i>N</i> =31 community-dwelling veterans w/ HF VA Medical Ctr.; Iowa City, IA	IV: Use of wt.-monitoring tool & modified Borg scale to rate SOB. Wt-monitoring tool had green-yellow-red zones (green=current wt.; yellow=2# wt gain-"take action"; red=5# wt. gain - "call doctor") DV--Primary outcomes - Quantitative: - Adherence to daily use of graphs (visual inspection of graphs) - HF Self-care (SCHFI) - Contacting providers & sx reported (weekly phone interviews) Secondary outcomes: - Actions taken (weekly phone interviews) Qualitative:	Primary outcomes: - Most participants used the 2 self-monitoring tools (mean use rate [SD] 79.9 [6.4] days). - Participants with potential exacerbations rarely took action (contacted their provider) based on use of tools. - No significant effect on HF self-care behaviors. Conclusions/Recommendations: - New strategies & instruments needed to promote pt.-clinician partnership & engage pts. in sx monitoring & recognition.

	<p>Secondary: - Actions taken in response to sx - Perceptions of usefulness of 2 graphs</p>		<p>- Perceptions of usefulness of graphs (final phone interview) Semi-structured baseline & completion interviews based on Situation-specific Theory of HF Self-Care</p>	<p>- While pts. are willing & able to track sx, they may need more intensive self-mgmt. support to take action based on their sx.</p>
<p>Examine association between enhanced care coordination & pt. self-mgmt. of HF (Shaw, O'Neal, Siddharthan, & Neugaard, 2014)</p>	<p>Prospective pilot-study IV: Set of care coordination strategies DV's--Primary outcomes: Self-mgmt. of HF after hospital discharge Secondary outcomes: 90-day HF readmissions; 30-day ED visits</p>	<p>N=40 pts. (20 in IG; 20 in CG; not randomly assigned) James A. Haley Veterans Hospital; Tampa, FL</p>	<p>IV: Care coordination per nurse facilitator: - Education of IG pts. re: HF prognosis, sx, diet, self-monitoring using green-yellow-red zone tool (on refrigerator magnet); list of HF resources at hospital and HF organizations. - Teach-back method used - Verified transportation to/from f/u MD appt., if Rx obtained at discharge - Post-discharge phone call to IG & CG pts. DV's--Primary outcomes: Phone call by nurse facilitator 48-96 hours after discharge w/ questions re: wt., BP, diet, meds, HF signs & sx, f/u MD appts. Secondary outcomes: 90-day HF readmissions; 30-day ED visits (chart review?)</p>	<p>IG pts. had signif. greater incidence of: - Had scale at home - Weighed self daily - Recorded weight - Practicing new/different health behaviors IG pts. had fewer 90-day readmissions & 30-day ED visits (not statistically significant) Conclusions/Recommendations: - Intensive education & care coordination improved self-mgmt. of wt., a key factor in reducing HF readmissions</p>
<p>Assess pt. acceptance of a Home Automated Telemonitoring (HAT) system for HF pts. (Finkelstein & Wood, 2014)</p>	<p>Feasibility study IV: Home Automated Telemonitoring (HAT) system for HF pts. DV's: Ease of use & convenience of HAT system</p>	<p>N=10 pts. Johns Hopkins Chronic Disease Informatics Pgm. Baltimore, MD</p>	<p>IV: HAT system (Laptop or Wii console) + digital scale, both connected to web-based care mgmt. portal. System enabled pts. to run self-test w/ set of HF sx questions, wt. check, send info to server, test their HF knowledge, receive feedback re: their current condition & educational "tip of the day". DV: Post-use survey of demographics, attitudes re: HAT system; qualitative interview</p>	<p>- 100% of pts. reported no difficulty w/ using HAT system or answering sx diary questions. - Pts. liked HF education portion of HF self-test, as they wanted to learn more about their condition. - Positive feedback re: content & interface. - 70% preferred Wii unit to laptop.</p>

Note: Tables organized in order of appearance in text of project report.

Abbreviations: APRN's = Advance Practice Registered Nurses; Appts. = Appointments; BP = Blood Pressure; CG = Control Group; CI = Confidence Interval; CINAHL = Cumulative Index of Nursing & Allied Health Literature; DHFKS = Dutch Heart Failure Knowledge Scale; DV = Dependent Variable; DVD = Digital Video Disc; ED = Emergency Department; GDS = Geriatric Depression Scale; HF = Heart Failure; HFKT = HF Knowledge Test; HFQoL = HF-related

Quality of Life; HFSPS = HF Symptom Perception Scale; HFSS = Heart Failure Symptom Scale; HRQoL = Health-Related Quality of Life; ICT's = Information & Communication Technologies; IG = Intervention Group; Inpt. = Inpatient; IV = Independent Variable; KCCQ = Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire; LTC = Long-term Care; MAQ = Metamemory in Adulthood Questionnaire; MDS = Multi-disciplinary; Mgmt. = Management; MHDHRQLI = MacNew Heart Disease Health-Related Quality of Life Instrument; MLWHFQ = Minnesota Living With Heart Failure Questionnaire; Mod. = Moderate; Mos. = Months; MOS = Medical Outcomes Study; NIHT = Non-invasive home telemonitoring; Outpt. = outpatient; PAM = Patient Activation Measure; PCP = Primary Care Provider; Pgm. = program; PI = Principal Investigator; Pt. = Patient; Pts. = Patients; QoL = Quality of Life; RCT = Randomized Control Trial; RR = Risk ratio; SCHFI = Self-Care of Heart Failure Index; SES = Socio-economic status; SFHS = Short Form Health Survey; signif. = statistically significant; SOE = Strength of evidence; STS = Structured telephone support; sx = symptoms; TCI's = Transitional care interventions; UC = usual care (for CG); VA = Veterans Affairs; w/ = with; Wt. = Weight